

NON-FORMAL EDUCATION MANUAL

Activities for the Digital Capacitation
and Integration of Young Migrants

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CONTENTS

1.Introduction	3
2.YouthConnect Project	5
3.The Needs that Shaped this Manual: YouthConnect Inquiry	9
a.Translation of Needs to Developed Activities (the role of the youth worker)	12
4.Session Plans	13
a.My Digital Life Map	14
b.Basic Digital Skills Workshop	20
c.The Basics of Canva	25
d.Storytelling: Building Our Story Together	30
e.JobQuest CV Workshop: From Current CV to Dream CV	34
f.Navigating Public Administration	40
g.Digital Inclusion and Online Safety	46
h.AI Tools and Ethical Prompting for Everyday Life	53
i.Digital Escape Room: Migrant Pathway	59
j.Opportunity Navigator: Finding Courses, Jobs and Local Support Online	62
k.Digital PeddyPaper (ActionBound)	66
5.Conclusions	73
6.Contacts	75

01. INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

For young migrants and refugees, **digital exclusion cannot be a secondary issue**. It can affect how they access information, communicate, find new opportunities, understand their rights, use public services, protect themselves online, and build an independent life in their new community. Low digital confidence is often linked to other barriers at the same time: language difficulties, limited access to devices or stable internet, lack of guidance, unfamiliarity with local systems, and fear of making mistakes in important online processes. In practice, this means that digital disadvantage can deepen social exclusion, reduce access to employment and learning opportunities, and increase vulnerability in daily life. YouthConnect was created in response to this reality, with the understanding that digital inclusion is not only about technology, but also about language, confidence, access, safety, participation, and rights.

This manual was developed to **support youth workers, educators, facilitators, and organisations working with young migrants and refugees in a more prepared, safe, and effective way**. Its purpose is not simply to promote the use of digital tools, but to help educators use non-formal education as a practical and human-centred methodology for strengthening autonomy, online safety, community integration, and access to professional opportunities. Within this manual digital skills were approached as everyday life skills: skills that can help a young person create and manage an email account, understand online public services, prepare a Europass profile, search for opportunities, organise information, communicate more independently, and navigate digital spaces with greater awareness and protection.

Non-formal education is the methodological core of this manual. The activities are designed around **learning by doing, participation, reflection, peer exchange, creativity, and practical problem-solving**. This approach is especially relevant when working with young migrants and refugees, because digital learning cannot be separated from confidence, language, access, safety, and lived experience. Instead of offering rigid instructions or one-size-fits-all lessons, the manual provides flexible activities that facilitators can adapt to different groups, contexts, and levels of digital competence. In this sense, the manual is not only a collection of digital activities, but a practical youth work tool to support inclusive, empowering, and real-life-oriented digital learning.

The manual is composed of **11 non-formal education activities** designed to be practical and adaptable. The activities combine digital learning with reflection, peer support, creativity, problem-solving, and real-world tasks. They address areas such as mapping personal digital skills, using basic digital tools, creating digital content, building CVs and employability profiles, navigating public administration, staying safe online, using AI critically, and expressing personal stories through digital methods. **Each activity includes specific objectives, methodologies, a general description, step-by-step facilitation guidance, lists and links to resources, duration, and inclusion and accessibility notes.**

02. YOUTHCONNECT PROJECT

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YOUTHCONNECT PROJECT

YouthConnect is an **Erasmus+ co-funded Small-scale Partnership in Youth** (2024-1-PT02-KA210-YOU-000252927) created to **strengthen the inclusion of young migrants and refugees through digital skills development and to improve the capacity of youth workers and educators who support them**. At its core, the project responded to a simple but urgent reality: in today's societies, digital participation is part of everyday participation. Accessing information, communicating with institutions and searching for work increasingly depend on digital confidence and competence. For many young migrants and refugees, these demands are added to the challenges of adapting to a new language, a new system, and a new social environment. YouthConnect was designed to respond to this intersection in a practical way, using youth work and non-formal education to turn digital learning into something accessible, relevant, and directly connected to real life.

Fundão Municipality

Estrellas del Sur

CEIR Latvia

The project brought together a consortium from **Portugal, Spain, and Latvia**, combining three complementary perspectives. In **Fundão, Portugal**, the **Municipality of Fundão** contributed with strong local experience in youth work, migrant inclusion, and cooperation with public services and community actors. In **Córdoba, Spain**, **Estrellas del Sur** brought experience in non-formal education and digital skills development with young people, including those facing barriers to participation. In **Riga, Latvia**, **CEIR** contributed with its background in educational research, innovation, and work with young people with fewer opportunities, including migrants and refugees. This complementarity is one of YouthConnect's main strengths. The project was not built only as a training initiative, but as a shared learning and development process that intended to connect local practice, educational methodology, and research-based reflection. In that sense, YouthConnect went beyond a narrow Erasmus+ project logic and positioned itself as a model of cross-sector cooperation that can inspire future work in the field.

YouthConnect was developed as a dual-capacity project. On one side, it seeks to support **young migrants and refugees** in gaining digital competences that matter for autonomy, online safety, employability, and integration into local communities. On the other, it seeks to equip **youth workers, educators, and institutions working with migrants and refugees** with better tools, methods, and confidence to respond to those needs. Around this core, the project also involves **local young people, public authorities, schools, migrant support institutions, stakeholders, and community actors**, recognising that inclusion does not happen through isolated action. It happens when support systems, learning spaces, and communities are able to respond more effectively and more inclusively. YouthConnect therefore understands integration not only as a question of adaptation by migrants and refugees, but also as a question of preparedness by the environments that receive them.

A defining feature of YouthConnect was the strong reliance on **non-formal education** as the pedagogical core of the project, not treating it as an accessory methodology, but as the main path to develop learning experiences, participation, and change. Throughout YouthConnect, digital competences were approached through active, participatory, and human-centred methods that invited young people to explore, create, reflect, practice, and collaborate. This includes work on basic digital skills, digital safety, access to opportunities, creative digital expression, and the use of innovative tools in dynamic and approachable ways. The project also opens space for the use of contemporary digital approaches, including AI-related awareness and innovative digital tools, always in a way that remains understandable, practical, and relevant to participants' everyday realities. By doing this, YouthConnect treats digital learning not as a technical transfer of information, but as a process of empowerment built through interaction, trust, and meaningful participation.

YouthConnect Project Team during the Kick-Off Meeting in Latvia (QMB and IT)

Another important strength of YouthConnect is: it was designed not only to implement activities, but also to generate **reusable and adaptable educational value**. The project included an inquiry research activity to better understand the needs of young migrants and refugees and of the professionals who work with them, but it didn't stop there. That knowledge was translated into educational responses, digital non-formal education tools, training processes, workshops, creative methods, and open-access resources that can continue to be used beyond the project itself.

YouthConnect Training Course in Cordoba

Through this approach, YouthConnect aimed to contribute to five concrete changes.

- First, it sought to strengthen the digital autonomy of young migrants and refugees in areas that affect daily life, safety, and opportunity.
- Second, it aimed to improve the ability of youth workers and educators to support these young people through practical and responsive digital youth work methods.
- Third, it worked to create more inclusive learning spaces where local youth and young migrants can meet, create, and learn together.
- Fourth, it contributed to the development of more innovative and adaptable non-formal education practices, including the use of creative digital tools and methodologies.
- Fifth, it strengthened cooperation between organisations, public actors, and community-based stakeholders so that digital inclusion is addressed not as an isolated workshop topic, but as part of a broader process of social and professional integration.

This is what gave YouthConnect its social relevance and its value as a good practice model: it connects people, methodology, and purpose in a way that is grounded in youth work and usable beyond the project itself.

03. THE NEEDS THAT SHAPED THIS MANUAL: YOUTHCONNECT INQUIRY

THE NEEDS THAT SHAPED THIS MANUAL: YOUTHCONNECT INQUIRY

The YouthConnect manual was shaped by the realities identified through the project inquiry, not by assumptions alone. Across Fundão, Córdoba, and Riga, the inquiry gathered **223 valid responses**, including **153 young migrants and refugees** and **70 youth workers / professionals from institutions working with migrants and refugees (IWMRs)**.

The findings showed a clear pattern: the main issue was not lack of interest in digital learning, but unequal conditions for taking part in it. Most young migrants were already online every day (**78.4%**) and many showed strong interest in digital learning (**68.6%**), yet almost half did not have their own laptop or computer (**47.7%**), and more than half had already been blocked from completing online tasks for school, training, or work because of access or technical problems (**35.9% yes and 20.9% sometimes**). This confirmed that digital exclusion in this context is deeply structural: being “connected” does not necessarily mean being able to participate effectively, safely, or independently.

The inquiry also made the main barriers very visible. Among young migrants and refugees, the strongest barriers were **financial cost (42.5%)**, **not knowing where to learn (37.9%)**, and **needing mentor or human support (32.7%)**, followed by **lack of devices (28.1%)** and **language barriers (24.2%)**. Professionals confirmed the same pattern as the young people they work with: the most common constraints they identified were young people’s **irregular access to devices or internet (50.0%)**, **limited resources in services (45.7%)**, and **language and translation barriers (40.0%)**. Taken together, these results showed that the needs behind this manual were not only about teaching digital tools. They were about reducing practical obstacles, making learning easier to enter, and designing activities that do not depend on ideal conditions that many participants simply do not have.

When the inquiry looked at what young migrants and refugees most wanted to learn, three priorities stood out clearly: **job search and CV tools (57.5%)**, **basic computer and internet skills (51.0%)**, and a third area that points beyond basic survival needs alone: **AI tools and creative design/storytelling tools (both 42.5%)**. This was important, because it showed that participants were not only asking for support to “catch up,” but also for tools that could help them express themselves, build confidence, and engage with the digital world in more future-oriented ways. At the same time, the inquiry identified weaker confidence in **privacy and personal data protection (35.7% low confidence)**, which made online safety another essential need.

On the youth workers and professionals’ side, the strongest priorities were **supporting young people with online public and social services (82.9%)**, **CVs and online job profiles (81.4%)**, and **basic computer and internet skills (77.1%)**, alongside high demand for **safe and respectful online communication (71.4%)** and **AI-related use and ethics (68.5%)**. These findings gave the manual a very clear direction: it needed to connect employability, autonomy, access to services, digital safety, and creative digital participation in one coherent learning pathway.

For that reason, the manual was built around practical non-formal education activities that respond directly to these needs. Its activity objectives, methodologies, and facilitation choices were shaped by evidence from the inquiry: a preference for **in-person workshops (35.3%)** and **blended learning (22.2%)** over **online-only formats (19.0%)**, the importance of mentor support, and the need for learning that works in real-life conditions. This is why the manual prioritises step-by-step tasks, clear real-world purposes, visual guidance, repetition, safe group processes, and space for support rather than assuming high confidence from the start. It is also why the activities include adaptations for phone-based participation, mixed digital starting points, language-sensitive facilitation, privacy-conscious practice, and inclusive support measures that make participation more realistic for young migrants and refugees facing structural barriers. In short, the inquiry did not simply inform the manual, it determined its content, its pedagogical choices, and its commitment to accessible, relevant, and evidence-based digital inclusion work.

Digital Learning Priorities according to inquired young migrants (percentage - %)

Digital Learning Priorities according to inquired youth workers (percentage - %)

Preferred Learning Formats

TRANSLATION OF NEEDS TO DEVELOPED ACTIVITIES (THE ROLE OF THE YOUTH WORKER)

The needs identified in the YouthConnect inquiry were translated into activities with a clear pedagogical logic. The need to map uneven starting points in confidence, access, and motivation led to **My Digital Life Map**, which helps participants identify what tools they already know, what they want to learn, and what first steps are realistic for them. The strong demand for employability-focused learning (especially around CVs, job search, and practical digital tasks) was translated into **JobQuest CV Workshop: From Current CV to Dream CV**, where participants work on CV improvement, employment vocabulary, realistic next steps, and safe use of AI for job-related tasks.

The identified need for online safety, privacy, and critical navigation shaped the digital safety session built around the **Digital Privilege Walk**, the **3-Click Rule**, and practical reflection on scams, misinformation, and unsafe online offers. At the same time, the interest in future-oriented and creative learning informed **AI Tools and Ethical Prompting for Everyday Life** and the manual's digital storytelling work, which respond to young migrants' interest in AI, expression, and communication while keeping safety, consent, and critical use at the centre. In this way, the activities do not simply "cover topics", they transform identified barriers and priorities into structured learning experiences with clear objectives, relevant methodologies, and practical application.

Within this process, the youth worker plays a central role as facilitator of inclusive learning. The value of these activities does not depend only on their design, but on how they are facilitated: with the ability to adapt pace, reduce barriers, create safety, and connect each task to participants' real lives. In YouthConnect, the youth worker is the person who helps transform an activity into a meaningful learning process, making room for different starting points, supporting participation without judgement, and ensuring that digital learning remains practical, accessible, and relevant. This is especially important in a manual built around non-formal education, where methodology, trust, and facilitation style are part of the learning itself. For that reason, this manual should be read not only as a set of activities, but as a tool for responsive youth work practice.

04. SESSION PLANS

MY DIGITAL LIFE MAP

This activity helps participants reflect on their current digital habits, confidence and learning needs in a simple and visual way. They identify tools they know, skills they want to improve, and small next steps for learning. It also helps facilitators understand participants' starting points without turning the session into a test.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

By the end of the activity, participants will be able to:

- **Map their awareness of digital tools** by placing digital tool logos into three categories: "I use it all the time", "I've heard of it, but don't know how to use it", and "Never heard of it".
- **Identify their current confidence in key digital skills** by placing skill cards into four categories: "I mastered this one", "I can't really do this one", "I really wanna learn this one", and "I don't know what it is, and I'm not very interested".
- **Reflect on their personal motivation to learn digital skills** by selecting at least three motivations, such as school, work, safety, language and communication, independence, creativity, problem-solving or future opportunities.
- **Create 2 to 3 realistic learning quests** by choosing digital skills they want to unlock and defining why they matter, how they will learn them, one first 30 to 60 minute mission, and how they will know they have learned them.
- **Share one learning mission with the group** to inspire peer learning and help youth workers identify common learning needs for future workshops.

METHODOLOGIES

Visual mapping

Self-assessment

Gamified learning quest

Peer support and buddy system

Guided reflection

Action planning

Group sharing

Facilitator observation and diagnostic assessment

Digital whiteboard use, with printable or analog adaptation available

Part 1. What Digital Tools do you know?
Digital skills shouldn't be scary, but we all need to start somewhere. What tools do you know? Put them in the appropriate box in the...

I've heard of it, but I don't know how to use it

Never heard of it?

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ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION

This activity helps young people reflect on their digital life in a simple and non-threatening way. It is not a test. It is a visual and participatory mapping exercise where participants identify what they already know, what they want to learn, and what small steps they can take to improve.

The activity can be implemented using the Canva whiteboard or with the printable handouts. The whiteboard version includes four parts: digital tools, digital skills, learning adventure, and a collective “Our Next Digital Moves” board. The printable version includes separate handouts for the matrices, digital skill cards, motivation sheet and quest cards, which can be used for offline or low-tech delivery

1. Welcome and safety frame

Start with an active energizer to get the jitters out of the way and have everyone’s attention levels, as this activity is of a more reflexive and low intensity environment. If needed and you have enough time with your group, a mid session break or another short energizer halfway through can also go a long way.

Then explain the purpose of the My Digital Life Map activity:

“Digital skills shouldn’t be scary. We all start somewhere. Today we will map what we already know, what we want to learn, and what first steps we can take.”

Make clear that:

- this is not an exam;
- there are no wrong answers;
- participants do not need to share private information;
- everyone can work with a buddy;
- participants can use simple words, icons or colours if writing in English is difficult.

Remind participants not to share passwords, ID numbers, bank details, private documents or sensitive personal information.

2. Quick whiteboard demo

Before starting the activity, show participants how to use the Canva whiteboard.

Demonstrate only the essential actions:

- **Zoom in/out:** Ctrl + / Ctrl - on Windows or ⌘ + / ⌘ - on Mac.
- **Move around the board:** hold Spacebar and drag the empty space, or use the trackpad/mouse.
- **Move items:** click once, hold, and drag logos or sticky notes.
- **Copy a sticky note:** select it and press Ctrl + D on Windows or ⌘ + D on Mac.
- **Edit text:** double-click inside a sticky note.
- **Undo a mistake:** Ctrl + Z on Windows or ⌘ + Z on Mac.

If working with a large group, prepare one copy of the three individual matrices for each participant or pair. Keep **Part 4: Our Next Digital Moves** as a shared group space.

Facilitator note: too many users or too many duplicated matrices may slow down the board. If the group is large or internet is unstable, use pairs or the printable version.

3. Part 1: What Digital Tools do you know?

Participants look at the digital tool logos and place them into one of three categories:

- **I use it all the time**
- **I've heard of it, but don't know how to use it**
- **Never heard of it**

Encourage participants to add tools that they know how to use, or have heard from before by searching adding an image of it's logo. In the digital version, they can upload logos or add sticky notes. In the paper version, they can write extra tools directly on the matrix.

Facilitator role:

- support participants who do not recognise some logos;
- encourage curiosity instead of embarrassment;
- ask light reflection questions, such as:
 - "Which tools do you use every day?"
 - "Which tool seems useful but unfamiliar?"
 - "Are there tools from your country that should be added?"

4. Part 2: What Digital Skills have you mastered?

Explain that knowing a tool and mastering a skill are not the same thing. For example, someone may use Gmail but not feel confident sending a formal email with an attachment. Participants read the digital skill cards and place them into one of four categories:

- **I mastered this one**
- **I can't really do this one**
- **I really wanna learn this one**
- **I don't know what it is, and I'm not very interested**

Participants can also add their own digital skills using blank sticky notes or paper.

Facilitator role:

- help participants understand difficult skills using examples;
- support translation or peer explanation when needed;
- avoid correcting participants' self-assessment unless they ask for help;
- pay attention to the skills most often placed in "I really wanna learn this one".

5. Part 3: Planning our Learning Adventure

This is the action-planning phase. Participants choose **2 to 3 skills** from the previous part that they want to “unlock”.

First, ask them to reflect on their motivation. They select at least three motivations, such as: School; Work; Problem-solving; Safety; Creativity; Language and Communication; Daily Life and Independence; Future Opportunities.

My Motivation

Work	
Safety	
Daily Life and Independence	
Future Opportunities	

Choose at least 3 motivations to learn a new skill. Then add a check to each of the motivations you chose!

1 Skill I want to unlock

Develop Presentations using Canva
HaslStar NGO

???

Why this matters to me:
It will help me do better in school and work. By being able to create visually appealing presentations for my papers and pitches.

How I will learn:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tutorial /Online	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> School or Uni	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Course/ e-learning	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Practice/ Learn-by-Doing
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HMM?

My first mission is to: in 30–60 minutes, I will watch a video on the basics of a good presentations and get started on my first class of Canva Design School

I will know I learned it when:
I can create a 20 page presentation on Canva that looks appealing without using a template

Then, for each chosen skill, participants complete a quest card with:

- **Skill I want to unlock**
- **Why this matters to me**
- **How I will learn**
- **My first mission is to: in 30 to 60 minutes, I will...**
- **I will know I learned it when...**

Encourage them to make their first mission small and realistic.

Examples:

- “In 30 to 60 minutes, I will send one email with an attachment to my buddy.”
- “In 30 to 60 minutes, I will convert one document to PDF.”
- “In 30 to 60 minutes, I will create three slides about myself.”
- “In 30 to 60 minutes, I will scan one document with my phone.”
- “In 30 to 60 minutes, I will identify two red flags in a job offer.”

Facilitator role:

- help participants make big goals smaller;
- ask: “Can you really do this in 30 to 60 minutes?”
- encourage clear evidence of learning;
- support participants to choose learning methods, such as tutorial, buddy, school/university, youth worker, AI-guided learning, course, workshop or learn-by-doing.

6. Quest Buddy Check

Participants work in pairs. Each person shares one quest card with their buddy.

The buddy asks:

- "Why do you want to learn this?"
- "Is your first mission small enough?"
- "Can you do it in 30 to 60 minutes?"
- "How will you know you learned it?"
- "What support do you need?"

This step helps participants improve their plan without turning it into a formal presentation.

7. Part 4: Our Next Digital Moves and closing

Each participant chooses one mission they want to share with the group and adds it to the collective board.

They share:

- what they want to unlock;
- their first small mission;
- what support they need.

This creates a visible group learning map. It also helps the youth worker understand the group's priorities.

Facilitator closing questions:

- "What skills appear many times?"
- "What support does the group need most?"
- "Which topics should we include in the next workshops?"

Close by reinforcing:

"This board is not a list of problems. It is a map of what this group wants to learn next."

RESOURCES

Digital version

- Canva whiteboard link: <https://canva.link/dexmvdm9qspy5cu>
- Internet connection
- Laptop, tablet or smartphone for each participant or pair
- Projector/screen for facilitator demonstration
- Digital tool logos (in whiteboard)
- Digital skill cards (in whiteboard)
- Quest cards (in whiteboard)
- Shared “Our Next Digital Moves” board (in whiteboard)

Analog / printable version (<https://canva.link/vh0v1w0eze9li15>)

- Printed A3 Part 1 matrix
- Printed A3 tool logos or blank cards
- Printed A3 Part 2 matrix
- Printed A3 digital skill cards
- Printed A3 motivation sheet/s
- Printed A3 quest cards
- Printed A3 or flipchart version of “Our Next Digital Moves”
- Pens, markers, tape, glue or sticky notes

Inclusion supports

- Pair work / buddy system
- Simple language instructions
- Visual examples
- Option to answer orally while a peer or facilitator writes
- Multilingual support or glossary where possible
- Offline paper version in case of weak internet or low digital confidence

Duration

120 minutes

For larger groups or lower digital literacy levels, extend to **150 minutes**.

BASIC DIGITAL SKILLS WORKSHOP

This activity introduces participants to basic digital tools and everyday digital tasks in a practical, hands-on way. It helps them build confidence with essential functions such as navigating platforms, creating simple documents, using email, and organising information. The focus is on learning by doing in a supportive environment.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

By the end of the activity, participants will be able to:

- **Navigate a cloud-based interface (Google Drive)** and perform three core actions: creating, naming, and sharing a document.
- **Create, format, and download a document in Google Docs** using basic text-editing features such as titles, bullet points, bold, colours, and highlights.
- **Use email and Google Calendar** for simple digital communication and organisation by attaching a PDF to an email, sending a short message, and saving an event in their calendar.

METHODOLOGIES

Guided digital demonstration

Learning by doing

Pair work

Collaborative task-based learning

Peer feedback

Gamified discovery

Digital communication practice

Guided reflection

ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION

Preparation before activity

Before the activity the facilitator should have the participants email addresses, so he/she can share the google drive folder where participants will work.

Also before participants entering the room the facilitator should prepare 6 hidden envelopes/papers with clues through the room or vicinity, these papers have written "Sports day event" "Friday" "From" "09:00 AM" "to" "15:00 PM".

The projector and the facilitators laptop should also be in place.

Energizer

Molecules

Participants walk freely around the room while the facilitator plays music or gives a simple movement instruction. **When the facilitator calls out a number**, for example "three" or "five", **participants must quickly form groups with that number of people**. After each round you can add a simple prompt for the group to answer, such as "say your name", "name one app you use every day", or "name one digital tool you want to learn better". After a few rounds, the facilitator shouts the final number (2) to create pairs or small working groups for the activity. This energizer helps participants move, interact, reduce tension and prepare for collaborative work.

Demo: The cloud

Using a projector, **begin by showing a Google Drive**. Then check the temperature in the room by asking whether anyone already knows or uses Google Drive, what they use it for, and if not what do they think it is. If some participants know it, invite them to explain it in their own words. Here's a simple metaphor we like to use:

"Google Drive is like a "digital backpack" that follows you everywhere. A place where you keep and organize your files so you can find them later."

After than it's time to **showcase Drive's main features:**

- how to create a new folder,
- how to name a folder,
- how to use the search bar
- how to share a folder or document,
- how to create a google docs, sheets, slides, etc.

Make this showcase as interactive as possible, try asking if participants know how to do it before showcasing a feature, and if someone knows, let the young person explain it to their peers and guide them through it.

Then the facilitator needs to prepare the next part of the activity live. **Create a shared folder and show how it can be shared with participants by email** (explain that this is what makes collaboration easy in Google Docs, sharing and working together in the same doc at the same time.) When sharing the folder with their email, you can also show how to send an email to several contacts at the same time.

Plan the Sports Day

After this initial interaction the facilitator should explain that participants will be creating a sports day together. Each pair will be in charge of **creating one sport event of their choice, but the local town hall asked them to send a Doc with the information about their sports activity**, so they should begin by creating a google docs.
(Each team opens a google docs in a shared drive)

The document for the Town Hall should include:

- a title for the activity
- what sports or games they can choose from
- what materials are needed
- where it will happen
- for how many people
- how long it will last
- a short description of the day/sport or how the game works

To practise the desired digital skills, **encourage participants to format the document using specific Google Docs features** such as:

- title
- different font size
- bold
- bullet points
- text colour
- highlighting the most important information
- Identifying the document in the header with their name and the name and logo of the organization

Participants will have 15/20 minutes to complete this task, the work should be done in teams, and the purpose is autonomous exploration of the digital tools, if there are any doubts try explaining and showing different features again live with the projector.

Shared feedback

After everyone finishes, participants are invited for a couple of minutes to enter in the google docs of their colleagues and leave some feedback using the feature "Comments".

If needed explain how to leave comments and then give your young Digital Wizards 5 minutes to explore the work done by the others and share some feedback

Send it via Email

In the next step participants will have to **download the document in PDF format, after changing the file name** to include the sport/event title that they choose followed by both team members names (e.g. *MAFIA_TOURNAMENT_ANDRE_PEDRO.pdf*).

Then participants should **send the pdf to the facilitator annexed to an email**. This email should follow the basic rules of email writing below that you can showcase by sharing your screen in the projector:

- Write a clear subject
- Start with a greeting
- Write a short message (Say why you are writing and what file you are sending)
- Mention the attachment
- Finish politely
- Write your name
- Check the email address
- Check the attachment

How to Send an Email with an Attachment

⇒ A quick guide for writing a clear, polite email ⇐

- 1 Before writing**
 - Check the email address
 - Write a clear subject
- 2 Write your email**
 - Start with a greeting
 - Write a short message
 - Say why you are writing
 - Say what file you are sending
 - Mention the attachment
 - Finish politely
 - Write your name
- 3 Before sending**
 - Check the attachment
 - Read your email again
 - Click send

Example email

To: ana@example.com
Subject: CV for today's activity

Hello Ana,
I am sending my CV for today's workshop task.
Please find the file attached.

Best regards,
Ahmed

CV_Ahmed.pdf
152 KB

Send

Quick reminder: Keep it short, clear and polite.

yc YouthConnect Co-funded by the European Union

Mark the dates in Google Calendar

For their final task, **participants got approval from the municipality** (if you have time while participants send you their emails w/ sports day plans, reply to them announcing the approval of their event). Now your Digital Wizards will have to start organizing themselves by **marking the event on their google calendar and sharing it with you and their team member**. Take the chance and explain exactly how it's done (click a date on google calendar, add an event, fill in the necessary fields).

However, your participants will surely notice that they weren't told at any time when the event will happen, or given freedom to schedule it. And this is where we will add a surprise twist.

Declare that **they have to search in the room/vicinity for the correct answer** and that the answer is locked inside **6 hidden envelopes**. Participants will then start searching for the clues. The papers inside the 6 envelopes say: "Sports day event" "Friday" "From" "09:00 AM" "to" "15:00 PM".

When they find all the papers have them schedule their events in the google calendar finishing the activity.

Closing

To close the activity, **invite your participants to stop using their devices and return attention to the group** (stepping away from the computers and making a circle with everyone is a cool touch).

Guide the group through their reflection about the activities and the tools that they used for the last 80–90 minutes. A good rule of thumb for debriefings is going through the 3W's of reflection:

1. **What Happened?** (What did they just do and what happened in the process)
2. **So What?** (What consequences came from what happened)
3. **Now What?** (Now that we know those consequences/learnings/happenings what can we take with us moving forward)

Your job is not to tell them directly the answer to these questions, but guide them into the correct answer and creating clear direct links between the abstract of the activity and young people's daily lives.

Here's some extra support questions for debriefing:

- What new thing did you learn today?
- Where could you use these digital skills in real life?
- After this activity, what do you feel more confident doing?

At the end in a circle every participant completes the following sentence "Today I learned..."

RESOURCES

- Projector
- Laptop (Facilitator)
- 1 Laptop per each 2 youngsters
- Internet (Wi-Fi)
- Smartphones
- 6 printed clue papers (1. "Sports day event" 2. "Friday" 3. "From" 4. "09:00 AM" 5. "to" 6. "15:00 PM".)
- Envelopes, Tape or material to hide/fix the clues in the room/venue
- Participant email list
- Short explanation of basic email writing rules: <https://canva.link/8uasc6eyz2sm8sl>

Inclusion and Accessibility Notes for the Facilitator

- Start slowly and demonstrate each task step by step, checking that participants can follow before moving on.
- Offer pair or buddy work so participants can support each other, especially when device confidence or language levels differ.
- Use simple language, visual examples and repeated instructions rather than long explanations or technical terms.
- Prepare a low-tech or printed alternative for key steps in case devices, internet access or accounts become a barrier.
- Avoid making participants feel embarrassed about not knowing "basic" things, and normalise asking for help throughout the activity.
- Make sure participants do not share passwords, personal emails, private files or other sensitive information during the session.

Duration
100 min

THE BASICS OF CANVA

This activity introduces participants to the basic functions of Canva through guided exploration and hands-on creation. Working in small groups, they learn how to use templates, elements, uploads and simple design tools to create a poster, social media post or logo. The session focuses on creativity, experimentation and building confidence with a practical digital tool.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

By the end of the activity, participants will be able to:

- **Navigate the basic Canva interface** by identifying and using at least four key sections, such as templates, elements, uploads, text tools, design tools or Magic Media.
- **Create a simple visual product in Canva**, such as a poster, social media post or logo, using basic design functions including text, images, icons, shapes, colours and fonts.
- **Apply basic visual communication principles** such as readability, contrast, visual hierarchy, alignment, margins and white space to make their design clearer and more attractive.
- **Experiment with Canva features independently or in teams**, including templates, uploaded media, effects, animations, grouping, locking, positioning or AI-generated elements, according to their digital confidence level.
- **Use Canva as a tool for self-expression and communication** by creating a design connected to a real idea, event, message, personal interest or social issue that they want to share with others.
- **Present their final design and explain their creative process**, naming at least two Canva tools they used, one design choice they made, and one thing they would improve with more time.

METHODOLOGIES

Learning by doing

Demonstration and guided practice

Experiential learning

ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION

Welcome participants and open the session with a short energizer called **Human Logo**. Everyone stands in a circle, says their name, and creates a simple “logo” using their body. This helps create a relaxed atmosphere and introduces the idea that design is a practical and creative skill that everyone can learn.

After the energizer, introduce the objective of the workshop: participants will learn the basic functions of Canva and use them to create a simple, attractive visual product. Explain that Canva can be used for different purposes, such as:

- presentations for school or university;
- logos;
- social media posts;
- posters.

Then briefly introduce Canva using simple and motivating language:

“Canva is your creative digital tool for making anything look professional without needing a degree in design. It is a drag-and-drop playground where you can turn a blank screen into a social media post, a school presentation, or a wallpaper for your phone in minutes.”

“Who wants to try it?”

Next, divide participants into groups of 3 or 4, depending on the number of devices and the size of the group. Ask each group to log into Canva on their computer and support anyone who needs help accessing the platform. Once everyone is ready, start exploring the Canva website together.

Tutorial Section

Begin by presenting the Canva sidebar and explaining the most important sections.

Templates

Explain that templates are pre-designed layouts that participants can use for inspiration, guidance, or direct adaptation. They can help users start more easily, especially when they do not know how to organise their design.

Remind participants: *“The template is just a suggestion. You can change it, adapt it, delete parts, or use it only as inspiration.”*

Elements

Explore the different element categories and show how to add them to a blank page. Demonstrate how to insert images, icons and shapes, change colours and fonts, move elements around the page, and organise information in a clear visual way.

Uploads

Show participants how to upload a photo or video from their computer and use it inside their Canva design.

Tools

Present some additional Canva tools, such as tables, sticky notes, drawing tools and simple graphics. Keep this part short and practical, focusing only on what participants may use in their own designs.

Magic Media

Introduce Magic Media as Canva's AI image generator. Use playful and creative prompts to show how it works, such as:

"Create an elephant eating pizza on the beach."

or

"Generate a crocodile driving a flying car."

After each short demonstration, give participants time to repeat the same step on their own screen. Keep the rhythm simple and practical. Make sure nobody is left behind, avoid technical language when possible, and use visual examples to support understanding.

Logo Creation Demonstration

After exploring the basic tools, demonstrate the process of creating a simple logo. Use this moment to show different Canva features in action, such as:

- uploading an image to use as a background;
- reducing the background image opacity to 40% using transparency;
- adding AI-generated images;
- using 3D elements;
- applying effects;
- animating three elements;
- duplicating elements;
- locking and grouping figures or elements;
- using the copy style feature;
- changing the position of elements by moving layers;
- using the alignment feature.

Pro tip: Select multiple items, click **Position**, and then use **Tidy Up** to organise elements neatly. While creating the logo, introduce simple design tips that participants can apply immediately.

Respect safe zones/margins

"Keep all your important information, such as text, logos and buttons, at least 15–20 mm away from the edges."

Show participants how to use Canva margins as a practical hack.

Visual hierarchy

"Always prioritise what you want your audience to notice first."

Explain that the headline should usually be the biggest text, the subheadline medium-sized, and the body text smaller.

Squint test

Ask participants to squint their eyes until the design looks blurry and ask: "What is the first thing you see?"

If the most important information is not visible first, they may need to adjust size, colour or position.

Rule of thirds

"Imagine your canvas is divided into a 3x3 grid. Place your most important focal point, such as a person's eyes or a product, near the lines or intersections."

White space is your friend

"White space is not wasted space. It makes the design easier to read and helps guide the eye to what matters."

If a design feels too crowded, encourage participants to remove one element.

Contrast is king

If the background is busy or dark, show how to place a semi-transparent shape behind the text. For example, a black rectangle at 40% opacity behind white text can make the message easier to read without hiding the image.

At the end of the demonstration, show how to present the project, adapt the format to different needs, and download the final result.

Hands-on Workshop

Once the basic functions have been introduced, invite participants to create their own design. They can choose one of three options:

- a poster;
- a social media post;
- a simple logo.

Participants work in teams and apply the tools they have just explored. Encourage them to create something useful and realistic, such as a poster for an event they would like to organise with friends, a local event in their town, a social media post about a social issue, or a visual announcement for a sport activity.

During the creation phase, which should last around **50 to 55 minutes**, move around the room, support each group, answer questions, and help participants improve both the technical and visual aspects of their work. Guide them when needed on how to make their content more readable, avoid overcrowding the design, and choose colours, fonts and images that match their message.

Toward the end of the session, ask participants to finalise and save their work. Then invite them to briefly present their design to the group or in pairs. During the presentation, they should explain what they created and mention which Canva tools they used. This sharing moment helps reinforce learning, visibility and confidence.

Debriefing and Closing

To close the activity, invite participants to reflect on what they learned while using Canva, how they felt during the creative process, and how digital design can help them communicate ideas more clearly. The focus should be on confidence, experimentation, problem-solving and possible real-life uses of Canva.

Questions to ask participants:

- What Canva tool or feature did you learn to use today?
- What was easy, and what was difficult?
- How did you feel while experimenting with Canva?
- What design choice improved your final product?
- Where could you use Canva again in real life?

RESOURCES

- Computers/Laptops (at least 1 per 3 participants) + 1 for facilitator
- Projectors
- Visual elements to illustrate
- Presentation Link: <https://canva.link/rfyf2b0cw1sd01>

Inclusion and Accessibility Notes

- Start with **templates instead of a blank page** for participants who feel stuck, have lower confidence, or are overwhelmed by too many design choices.
- Offer **small-group or buddy roles** such as clicking, reading, choosing images, or checking layout, especially if one participant has weaker language skills or less experience using a computer.
- Keep the task flexible: if one group finds logo creation too difficult, allow them to make a **simpler poster or social media post** instead.
- Use **visual demonstration and repeat each step slowly**. If participants get lost in the Canva sidebar, focus only on the core tools they need first: template, text, elements and download.
- If internet, login access or devices become a barrier, use a **paper-based version** where participants sketch their design first and a peer or facilitator later recreates it in Canva. This keeps the creative goal without excluding anyone.
- Avoid judging designs by how “professional” they look. Focus feedback on **clarity, message and progress**, so participants do not feel ashamed if their design is simple or unfinished.

Duration

120 min

- Energizer - 10min
- Introduction - 5/10 min
- Platform exploration - 25/30 min
- Logo creation and digital tips - 15/20 min
- Participants exploration - 50/55 min
- Small debrief - 10/15 min

STORYTELLING: BUILDING OUR STORY TOGETHER

This activity uses collaborative storytelling to help local youngsters and young migrants build shared narratives through images, reflection and group creativity. It supports self-expression, communication and connection by inviting participants from different backgrounds to co-create meaning together. The focus is on participation, imagination and respectful listening rather than on perfect language or performance. There's a support slide presentation to support facilitation in the resources section as well!

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

By the end of the activity, participants will be able to:

- **Use visual language and expression to represent strengths, interests and identity elements** in a safe and creative way, by selecting at least three images, icons or colours that can inspire fictional characters or story elements.
- **Develop clear visual communication and active listening skills** through a paired Canva task, where one participant explains a triptych using simple descriptions and the other recreates it by interpreting, asking questions and applying basic design tools.
- **Develop short collaborative visual stories using digital design tools (Canva)**, by creating a three-panel triptych that presents fictional characters, a challenge they face, and the way they respond, cope or move forward together.

METHODOLOGIES

Visual Intepretation

Intercultural peer learning

Paired visual communication/ expression task

Active listening and descriptive communication

Collaborative visual storytelling

Creative expression through Canva

Peer sharing and guided reflection

STORYTELLING: BUILDING OUR STORY TOGETHER

ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION

Energizer "Name Gangster"

To begin the session an energiser should be done to help the participants learn their names as, most probably, it will be the first time the young locals and migrants meet. Make a big circle mixing local people and young migrants. Then inform participants that in turns everyone will say their name outloud. The facilitator should be standing in the middle of the circle and your job is to be the 'gangster'.

Everytime you point at a participant, he/she should crouch down down, this is a trigger for the people standing to the right and left of the participant who crouched have shout each other's name. The slowest one to shout is eliminated. The game continues until there are only two participants remaining who would be the winners, or they do a final round gunslinger round to see who says each other's name faster.

Image Interpretation (Art and expression don't need words)

During the first part of the session, we will focus on **understanding how art is subject to the interpretation of the beholder!** As the level of Spanish/Portuguese/Latvian may not be very high in some cases, we propose the following alternative for this part of the session.

Begin with image interpretation. The slide presentation of this activity includes a set of images and icons showing different situations, environments and qualities, such as a busy kitchen, an office, a construction site, a clock, a puzzle or a handshake. Instead of starting with words, first ask participants to observe the images and reflect on what each one could represent.

Bonus points if you invite your youngsters to choose the images that connect with them personally and explain why: what skill, quality, feeling or experience does this image suggest? Trainers and local participants support the discussion by helping them transform visual interpretations into simple words or adjectives, such as "responsible", "creative", "organised", "versatile" or "committed".

What Do You See Here?

After the first part of the session and the energiser, participants should already feel more comfortable with each other, or at least know some names. At this point, create mixed pairs with one local participant and one young migrant.

The second part of the session introduces the use of Canva for visual communication and storytelling. **Before starting the task, explain what a triptych is:**

"A triptych is a visual composition divided into three connected parts or panels. These three panels are usually seen together and tell one complete idea, story or message."

In this activity, the triptych will work like a short visual story: the first panel introduces the character/s, the second panel presents a challenge or problem, and the third panel shows a solution, response or way forward.

To help participants understand the format, **show the different examples of triptychs in the powerpoint**, starting with simple ones and then moving toward more artistic or complex examples. Pass the ball to participants to observe and interpret the meaning of the triptychs like how the three panels may be connected through their different colours, images, symbols, characters or emotions displayed.

Then we move to practice, **give each pair a printed example of a triptych**, but **only one of them can see it**, and **the other one will have a computer and a blank Canva Design**. The participant holding the triptych will try to explain to his/her pair what they are seeing and whilst the participant with the computer should try to replicate it with Canva in **15 minutes**.

Create Your Own Triptych

Following this dynamic, the facilitator should give the participants **45 minutes** to create their own triptychs.

The idea is for participants to **create stories together** that reflect aspects of both the locals and the migrants, connect over expressing themselves together and overcome the challenges and barriers the process might bring. After the creation they will share it with their pairs.

The instructions should be:

- in the first matrix they have to introduce their characters, which should be them (the participant), represented by one image showcasing an ability that were chosen at the beginning
- the second matrix, a problem that may encounter their characters, based on true story of made up
- the third one, a solution or how they coped together and solved it

The 3 Panels of Your Story

Panel 1: THE CHARACTERS
Create fictional characters. Show their strengths, identity, interests or dreams.

Panel 2: THE CHALLENGE
Show a problem or barrier the characters face. It can be inspired by real life, but it does not need to be personal.

Panel 3: THE WAY FORWARD
Show how the characters respond together. What support, ideas or actions help them move forward?

After this moment the pairs will present their art pieces to other groups, reflect on their experience and the symbolic meaning of their artwork.

After presentations you can add some substance with some reflection questions:

- What does your story say about your pair?
- Which panel feels most important to you?
- What part was harder to express?
- How do you think this barrier/challenge affects people's lives?
- What did you discover about yourself while creating your story?

Four Questions Reflection

Participants stay in their pairs or small groups and briefly discuss four main questions:

- What did you learn about your partner?
- What surprised you about your own story? What about the stories of others?
- Which panel feels most important to you?
- What did you discover about yourself while creating your story?

RESOURCES

- Presentation Link: <https://canva.link/5njgxtknkrq5cn>
- Computers or laptops for participants
- 1 computer/laptop for the facilitator
- Stable internet connection
- Access to Canva for all participants/groups/pairs
- Projector
- Pre-opened Canva workspace or template, if you want to save time
- Triptychs Example for them to describe (<https://canva.link/u9ix9fdr0wyupw>)
- Printed Template triptychs (1 per group)

Inclusion and Accessibility Notes

- Allow participants to contribute through images, keywords, short sentences or oral ideas, especially if writing in English is difficult.
- If personal topics emerge, keep sharing optional and avoid asking anyone to explain private migration experiences or sensitive life situations.
- Offer pair or small-group support so participants can build the story together and help each other with language or confidence.
- If the activity feels too abstract for some participants, use a clear prompt, sample structure or visual sequence to make the task easier to follow.
- Focus feedback on participation, creativity and teamwork, not on grammar, storytelling style or speaking confidence.

Duration

120 minutes

JOBQUEST CV WORKSHOP: FROM CURRENT CV TO DREAM CV

This activity supports participants in improving an existing CV or building a stronger one based on their goals, skills and future aspirations. It helps them recognise what to include, how to present their experience clearly, and how to connect their profile to future opportunities. The focus is on practical improvement, confidence and employability.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

By the end of the activity, participants will be able to:

- **Recognise what employers look for in an application process** (CV, motivation letter, interview readiness) by identifying at least 4 good practices and 3 common mistakes and explain why they matter.
- **Build shared employment vocabulary** (CV, motivation letter, recruiter, job centre, hard/soft skills, etc.) by correctly matching at least 80% of the terms with their definitions in the vocabulary match-up game.
- **Create or improve a basic CV** leaving with an updated draft containing contact details, a short profile summary, skills, experience (including volunteering), education/training and languages spoken.
- **Practice visualizing career goals** by completing a "Dream CV" and writing one concrete action they will take within the next two weeks to move from their current profile toward that goal.
- **Use JobQuest AI** as a practical support tool in a safe, responsible and ethical by completing at least one guided AI task (e.g., improve summary, extract skills, tailor to an offer).

METHODOLOGIES

Case-based learning
(good/bad scenarios)

Guided group
discussion

Gamification

Individual work

Pair coaching/Peer
feedback

Reflective
brainstorming/Future-
planning

AI Workshop

Structured debriefing
and action planning

ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION

Preparation

Set the room for small-group work, place printed materials on a table (scenario cards, vocabulary cards, CV handouts), and open the PowerPoint deck that guides the whole session. Ensure Wi-Fi/data access and have the JobQuest QR/link ready on a slide. The PowerPoint is not only a guide.

Each mini-input segment contains the key content, examples and prompts you want participants to take home (good/bad practices, CV do's/don'ts, skill-building strategies, AI safety + prompts).

Energizer and Check-In

Start with a low-pressure energiser and a short check-in to understand the group's experience (job applications before, current situation, what feels hard). Keep the tone normalising and supportive: different starting points are expected.

Good practices vs bad practices: "Carl vs John" application scenarios

After the energiser and warm-up check-in, introduce the first practical task: comparing two fictional candidates, **Carl** and **John**, who are applying for the same job. The goal is to help participants understand which behaviours can increase or reduce someone's chances of being invited to an interview.

After a few minutes, bring everyone back together and collect their answers on a flipchart or slide with two columns: **what helps Carl** and **what makes John's application weaker**.

Close the discussion by highlighting that employers do not only look at experience. They also notice preparation, clarity, attention to detail, motivation and professional communication. This prepares participants for the next part of the workshop, where they will learn key employment vocabulary and start improving their own CVs.

JobQuest CV Workshop

Carl vs John
Who is more likely to get an interview?

Carl	John
Good application habits	Common mistakes
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Prepares before applying	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sends the same CV to every job
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Adapts CV to the job offer	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Does not read the offer carefully
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Writes a clear motivation message	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Forgets deadlines or documents
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Checks mistakes before sending	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Has unclear information in his CV
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Arrives on time and communicates clearly	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Does not prepare for the interview

Group question: Who has a better chance and why?

CARL - Good practices (what helps him get the job)

- Carl prepares for the interview by thinking of examples from his experiences and practising answers.
- Carl researches the organisation and the role, so he can explain why he wants this job and ask relevant questions.
- Carl tailors his CV to the job offer by highlighting relevant skills and using keywords from the ad.
- Carl prepares a motivation letter or cover message that links his experience to the job requirements.
- Carl is on time and communicates professionally (confirming details, polite tone, clear subject lines).
- Carl follows the application instructions (documents, format, deadline) and checks for mistakes before sending.

JOHN - Bad practices (what reduces his chances)

- John sends the same CV to every job without adapting it to the role.
- John does not research the company, so he cannot explain why he wants the job and looks unprepared.
- John's CV is unclear or incomplete (missing details, confusing structure, or irrelevant information).
- John skips the motivation letter/cover message or writes something generic that doesn't match the role.
- John is late or poorly organised (doesn't confirm interview details, misses deadlines, unclear communication).
- John doesn't check quality (typos, messy formatting, inconsistent dates) and may overshare unnecessary personal data.

Vocabulary match-up game

Tell participants that job-search systems often feel difficult because of unfamiliar words, and that understanding the vocabulary gives power and confidence.

In groups, participants match term cards to definition cards. After 5 minutes, correct quickly together using a slide that shows the right matches.

Definitions:

CV / Curriculum Vitae

A document that summarises your education, experience, skills and languages for job applications.

Motivation Letter / Cover Letter

A short letter explaining why you want the job and why your profile fits the role.

Job Application

The documents or forms you send to apply for a job, usually including a CV and sometimes a letter.

Job Offer / Job Advertisement

A published description of a job, including tasks, requirements, conditions and how to apply.

Interview

A conversation where the employer asks about your skills, experience and motivation for the job.

Recruiter

The person who reviews applications and helps choose candidates for a job.

Job Centre / Employment Office

A public service that supports people with job search, guidance, training and employment opportunities.

Hard Skills

Technical or practical abilities you can demonstrate, such as Excel, cooking, driving, Canva or machine operation.

Soft Skills

Personal and social abilities that affect how you work, such as communication, teamwork or reliability.

Transferable Skills

Skills gained in one context that can be useful in another, such as leadership, organisation or problem-solving.

Work Experience

Tasks and responsibilities from jobs, internships, volunteering or informal work that show what you can do.

Volunteering

Unpaid work that supports a community or organisation and can help develop skills and experience.

Internship / Traineeship

A temporary work-learning experience that helps you gain practical skills and understand a professional area.

Reference / Referee

A person who can confirm your skills, attitude or reliability if an employer asks.

Contract

A formal agreement that explains the job conditions, such as role, salary, hours, rights and responsibilities.

Portfolio

A collection of work examples that shows your skills, projects or achievements.

What a CV is + do's and don'ts

Shift from vocabulary to practice: explain that a CV is your "clear professional story," and employers often decide quickly whether to interview you based on clarity and relevance. Use the PowerPoint to show a simple CV structure and a "bad vs improved" example excerpt.

Core CV components: contact details; profile summary; skills; experience (paid + volunteering + informal responsibilities); education/training; languages; optional certificates/portfolio link.

CV do's: clear structure; short bullet points; action verbs; evidence; consistency; adapt to the job ad.

CV don'ts: sensitive data; messy layout; long irrelevant content; skills with no evidence; unclear dates.

Workshop Part A: "My Current CV" drafting

Distribute the Current CV handout and explain that the objective is a usable draft. Participants work individually or in pairs; facilitators circulate to support, especially translating informal experience into CV language.

Workshop Part B: "My Dream CV" reflection

Distribute the Dream CV handout and frame it as direction: what you would like your CV to look like in 2–3 years. Participants describe the role(s), experiences, and skills they want to add.

Skill-building strategies: bridging Current CV → Dream CV

Use slides to present realistic ways to build skills and experience, then ask participants to choose one strategy and write one action they can do soon.

Strategies menu (slide-based): education/training; online learning plans; volunteering; internships/traineeships; mentoring/youth worker support; portfolio building; job centre appointments/services.

JobQuest AI introduction + safe guided practice

Introduce JobQuest as support for concrete employment tasks (CV improvement, tailoring to job offers, motivation letters, interview prep, transferable skills, learning routes). Teach two simple safety rules: no sensitive data and always review/verify. Participants then complete one guided AI task using a prompt from the slide deck.

Debriefing and closing

Instead of ending with only a quick “what did you like,” you will guide participants through meaning-making (what happened), learning extraction (what I learned), and transfer (what I will do differently). This makes the session more transformative and reduces the risk that the workshop stays at “nice activity” level.

Debrief structure

Reconstruct what happened

Start with a simple group recap to anchor the experience:

- “What did we do today from start to finish?”
- “Which part felt easiest? Which part felt hardest?”

This helps participants organise the learning journey and notice progress.

Analyse Carl vs John: what really makes the difference?

Bring the group back to the scenario and go deeper than “good/bad”:

- “What are the real consequences of John’s choices in a recruiter’s mind?”
- “Which of Carl’s habits are the highest impact with the lowest effort?”
- “If you could only change one thing this week, what would it be?”

This helps prioritisation—participants focus on the few behaviours that bring the biggest improvement.

Personal learning: what did I discover about myself?

Ask participants to reflect individually for 1 minute (write on paper), then share in pairs:

- “What is one strength I already have that I can show better on my CV?”
- “What is one experience I used to think ‘doesn’t count’ but now I realise is valuable?”
- “What is one barrier (language, confidence, system knowledge, digital access) that affects me—and what support can I ask for?”

This can help build self-efficacy and helps participants reframe informal experience as legitimate learning.

Transfer to real life

Make the learning actionable and socially supported:

Each participant states one concrete next action (their two-week step) and one resource/person that can help (friend, youth worker, job centre, online course, mentor).

Optional “buddy system”: pair participants to check-in after one week.

Purpose: increases follow-through and turns intention into action

AI reflection: safe and critical use

Close by reinforcing AI as support, not authority:

- “What was useful about JobQuest today?”
- “What would you never share with it?”
- “How will you check if the output is good?”

Purpose: strengthens digital safety and critical thinking.

Closing line (facilitator):

“Your CV is not just a document, it’s a story of your skills and your direction; small habits like Carl’s, repeated consistently, change results.”

RESOURCES

- Room setup (small groups)
- Flipchart/markers
- Vocabulary cards
- Current CV handout and Dream CV handout (<https://canva.link/qu5im26pgahvzzb>)
- PowerPoint deck for each segment (<https://canva.link/duw8mvarxda2d4>)
- Projector/screen (recommended)
- Wi-Fi/data
- JobQuest QR/link (OUT SOON)
- Participant smartphones/laptops
- Inclusion supports (easy-language CV template, bilingual glossary/slides, pairing support)

Inclusion and Accessibility Notes

- Avoid asking participants to explain employment gaps, migration interruptions or personal circumstances in front of the group.
- Allow participants to work from a current CV, handwritten notes or memory, especially if they do not have a formal document with them.
- Offer simple templates, examples and vocabulary support for participants with lower language confidence or less experience with formal job documents.
- Use pair or buddy support for reviewing structure and clarity, but do not require anyone to share their full CV publicly.
- Remind participants that volunteering, informal learning, language skills and everyday responsibilities can also be valuable experience worth including.

Duration

120 min

NAVIGATING PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

This activity helps participants understand how to navigate public services and administrative systems in a more confident and structured way. Through practical examples, they explore how to identify the right service, follow basic procedures and understand common steps in administrative processes. The focus is on orientation, clarity and reducing anxiety around bureaucracy. This methodology was design around public administration services in Portugal, Spain and Latvia, if you are reading from another country, just download the resources and do slight adaptations to include the public insitutions/agencies of your country and you should be good to go! It's also easily usable for online-only contexts with minor adaptations!

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

By the end of the activity, participants will be able to:

- **Identify the main public agencies and services relevant to migrants** in their host country
- **Understand which agency to contact depending on different needs** and situations
- **Practise how to contact an agency**, request an appointment, and identify the main documents needed for the process
- **Prepare a basic administrative dossier** and identify where to get missing documents or support

METHODOLOGIES

Gamified station-based learning

Case-based simulation

Pair work and collaborative problem-solving

Guided digital exploration of official services

Administrative route mapping

Document analysis and dossier preparation

Learning by doing

Facilitator check-in and feedback

Reality-based reflection and debriefing

ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION

Preparation

Before the activity, prepare all the materials needed for the four stations and make sure each step of the simulation is ready to run smoothly. This includes printing the 7 role cards and preparing 7 copies of each template, one for each role/case used during the activity: the digital summary template for Station 1, the Route Card template for Station 2, the Contact Discovery Sheet and Document Checklist for Station 3, and the document dossier materials for Station 4. You should also organise the folder with official agency links, prepare the Canva whiteboard with the document bank, and review the answer key for each role card, so they can quickly check whether participants have chosen the correct administrative route. Before participants arrive, the room should be organised into clear working areas or stations, with computers or laptops ready, internet access tested, Canva and email access confirmed, and the projector prepared for instructions. It is also important to print or display the station instructions clearly and ensure that all examples are adapted to the correct country context: Portugal, Spain or Latvia.

How does the exercise work?

During this session, participants will learn about important public administration processes in their new countries (Portugal, Spain, or Latvia). Through a gamified simulation, they move in pairs through **4 different stations**, each one presenting a challenge related to administrative processes that migrants may face in their host country.

Participants will work in pairs. Each pair should receive a **role card** which describes a person from a migrant background, with a specific situation, needs, and available documents. The goal is to understand the case, identify the correct agencies, learn how to contact them, and prepare the necessary documents for an appointment. After making sure every pair understands the dynamics of the activity give participants around **5 minutes** to read their role and discuss the case.

After this introduction, the timer starts and participants will move through the 4 stations at their own pace.

Station 1 - Understand the Case and Create a Summary

Type: Semi-autonomous

Duration: 10 minutes

Format: Pair work on computer

The first station is supposed to help participants identify the core needs, missing elements, and first priorities of their assigned character before moving through the administrative route.

At this station, participants will open a digital summary template on the computer and after reading their role card carefully they should complete the template by identifying:

- basic information about the character
- the main needs or problems they identify
- what the character already has
- what seems to be missing
- what should probably be the first step

This is the “understand before acting” station. Its purpose is to help participants use critical thinking to analyse a situation before making any decisions.

Station 2 - Identify the Agencies and Build the Route

Type: Semi-autonomous, digital

Duration: 15 minutes

Format: Pair work on computer

The second station is meant to help participants understand the role of the main agencies and decide which ones are relevant for their case, and in which order.

At this station, participants will have to complete a **digital matching exercise**, where they connect each agency or office with its correct description. After matching agencies and descriptions, participants should look back at their role card and the summary from Station 1 to build a **Route Card** for their character. Here's a step-by-step:

Phase 1 - Understand the system

Participants match the agency categories with their functions/descriptions.

Phase 2 - Apply it to the case

Using their role card and the summary from Station 1, participants decide:

- which agencies are relevant for their case
- which one should come first
- which should come after
- which support service may help along the way

Categories / agencies / offices

- Migration / residence office
- Municipality / local registration office
- Health service / health registration office
- Employment office
- Education / training office
- Qualification recognition / certificate office
- Justice / criminal record office
- Migrant support or integration service
- Social Security
- Civil registration
- Family / child and youth services
- Tax / fiscal office

To move to Station 3, participants must send a screenshot of their completed Station 2 task to the facilitator through email.

Participants move then to the phase 3 to the facilitators desk.

Station 3 – Contact the Agency and Prepare the Appointment

Type: Facilitator-led + digital search

Duration: 20 minutes

Format: Pair work on computer + short interaction with facilitator

The third station is designed to help your participants learn how to contact the correct agency, identify the accepted form of contact, understand if an appointment is needed, and prepare the documents they must bring. When moving to this station, participants first need to approach the stations facilitator and check whether their Route Card priorities are correct.

Note: The facilitator has an answer key with the correct route for each role

- If the route is incorrect, participants must go back, correct it, and return to the station.
- If the route is correct, they continue to the next phase.

(here a line should be formed, and some participants will need to wait in the line. That's the objective, deal with waiting lines and bureaucracies is part of the experience of Public Administrative Process connected with migrations and integration)

After clearing the route check, participants will then access a **digital folder with official links** to the relevant agencies (they should only search freely on the internet with supervision from facilitators to ensure they are accessing updated info on official websites) and identify:

How each office/agency can be contacted

- online portal
- appointment platform
- email
- telephone
- physical desk
- support centre / help office

Whether an appointment is needed

- yes / no / depends

How the appointment is booked

- through portal
- by email
- by phone
- in person

What documents are usually requested

What details the person must provide

- name
- document number
- reason for appointment
- address
- contact information
- other information depending on the case

After finding this information, participants need to return to the facilitator and request the appointment.

Output of Station 3

Participants will have finished this station when the facilitator gives them (tip: you can send them in the form of an e-mail or printed handout for extra immersion!):

- an **Appointment Confirmation**
- a **Document Checklist** for the appointment

Station 4 - Build and Check the Document Dossier

Type: Semi-autonomous, digital

Duration: 20 minutes

Format: Pair work on Canva whiteboard

The final station is designed to help participants prepare the correct dossier for their appointment by identifying which documents they already have, which ones are missing, which ones are invalid, and where the missing documents can be obtained.

To solve their final challenge participants will access the station computer and open a **Canva whiteboard** prepared by the facilitator. On the whiteboard, they find a **document bank** with different documents related to their case. Some of them are correct and useful, some are missing, and some are wrong, incomplete, expired, or not needed.

Participants must drag the documents into the correct boxes on the whiteboard.

The Canva whiteboard includes 4 areas:

- **Ready to bring**
- **Missing**
- **Problematic / not valid**
- **Where do I get the missing documents?**

So in essence participants should begin by reviewing:

- what the appointment is for
- which agency they are going to
- which documents were identified as necessary in Station 3

Then they should sort the documents and connect each missing document with the correct source or agency. When the pair finishes, they call the facilitator for a final check.

Debriefing

After that adventure invite your participants to stop working and return their attention to the group. Focus the debriefing process on analyzing what happened during the simulation of administrative processes, whilst highlighting that real-life situations are often more complex, slower, and more stressful. The debriefing should help participants compare the activity with reality, reflect on what can make public administration processes difficult for migrants and what they can do to change/learn/avoid to excel at this processes, be protected and ready.

Here's some open questions you can use to help you guide the reflection process:

- What parts of the activity felt easiest, and what parts felt most confusing?
- What differences do you notice between completing the stations in a safe learning space and facing the same process in real life?
- What did you discover about the importance of preparing documents before contacting an office?

RESOURCES

- Presentation
- 1 to 4 facilitators (1 per station if possible)
- 7 role cards
- Digital summary template for Station 1
- Correct Route Cards / facilitator answer key
- Folder with official links to agencies' websites
- Contact Discovery Sheet for Station 3
- Document Checklist template
- Canva whiteboard
- "Where do I get it?" reference guide
- Debriefing questions
- Country adaptation sheet for Portugal / Spain / Latvia
- Computers or laptops for participants
- Facilitator laptop
- Projector
- Internet connection
- Email access
- Printed role cards
- Printed or digital station instructions

Annexes and Resources Pack

- Presentation link: <https://canva.link/vvbcowbls47803e>
- Analog Version Handouts: <https://www.canva.com/design/DAHKtd-d-nU/wqvqcdIGIGCuZzRvTgZWag/edit>
- Canva whiteboard: <https://canva.link/83mdxpzeeugt8bl>

Inclusion and Accessibility Notes

- Use fictional examples or sample cases rather than asking participants to work with their own legal, migration or administrative situation.
- Explain key terms in simple language and repeat important steps slowly, as bureaucratic vocabulary can be difficult or intimidating.
- Offer pair or small-group support so participants can discuss options together before making decisions in the activity.
- Avoid presenting the activity as legal guidance; keep the focus on how to navigate systems, ask questions and look for reliable information.
- If the process feels overwhelming, break it into small steps or visual sequences, and offer a printed/offline version of the main route or procedure.

Duration
120 min

DIGITAL INCLUSION AND ONLINE SAFETY

This activity helps young migrants reflect on their relation to their digital tools and learn good practices for safe, confident and informed use of digital tools and spaces. It introduces practical ways to recognise digital risks, make safer choices online and strengthen healthy everyday digital habits. The focus is on awareness, prevention and building confidence rather than fear.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

By the end of the activity, participants will be able to:

- **Recognise that digital inclusion is not only about owning a phone**, but also about access, skills, language, confidence, legal status, safety and social support.
- **Analyse how different migrant and youth profiles may experience digital life differently**, using fictional personas during the Digital Privilege Walk.
- **Identify common digital risks affecting young migrants**, such as misinformation, scams, fake job offers, privacy risks, surveillance concerns and unsafe requests for documents or money.
- **Apply the 3-Click Rule as a simple safety method before trusting online information**, offers, profiles or links.
- **Reflect on how digital tools can support autonomy and integration**, while also creating risks when people act under pressure, without support or without checking information.

METHODOLOGIES

Pair discussion

Persona-based simulation

Digital Privilege Walk

Scenario-based learning

Guided discussion

Digital safety analysis

Harm-reduction approaches

Critical thinking practice

Group reflection

ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION

Preparation before the activity

Before the activity, make sure you have a computer and a projector so you show the slide presentation, speakers (optional), a flipchart or whiteboard for notes and reflection w/ participants, markers, pens, pencils (optional) etc. Have a look at the Resources section for this part!

Next make sure you should print the annexed persona cards before the session or have them ready as images to text/email to participants. Each participant, pair or small group will receive one persona card.

Don't forget to prepare your activity room with enough open space for participants to move during the Digital Privilege Walk. You can also implement this part of the activity outdoors if it's easier and the weather allows for it. A line should be marked on the floor with tape, string or chairs. This will be the starting line for all participants.

Opening and framing

Begin by welcoming the group and explain that **the session will explore how digital tools can support migrants in everyday life, but also how they can create risks**. After letting your group know the plan for the day it's a good idea to do a short energizer with everyone, as we'll start with a slide presentation.

Then you can start projecting the slides and introduce the idea to the group that for many migrants, technology is not a luxury. A phone can be used for translation, maps, contacting family, booking appointments, looking for work, accessing public services or asking for help. At the same time, digital life can also expose people to scams, misinformation, surveillance, harassment and unsafe use of personal data.

Make sure to include some time to clearly present the safety rules of the workshop. Participants will not, and should not be asked, to share their own migration story, legal status or private information unless they wish to share so with the group. During the first activity (Digital Privilege Walk) they will use fictional personas, not their own identity.

After everyone is in the same page, begin by emphasizing:

"So today we are not learning technology just for the sake of technology. We are learning how digital tools can support autonomy, integration and safety."

Lifeline or Luxury?

Stop in the slide **"Lifeline or Luxury?"** and ask participants to discuss briefly in pairs:

- **When can a smartphone be a lifeline for a migrant?**
- **How can digital life be risky, become stressful, unsafe or excluding?**

After a few minutes of discussion, collect answers from the group and write them on a flipchart. Split it in two and:

- Under **Digital Lifelines**, participants may mention translation, maps, public transport, contacting family, job search, school communication, online banking, health appointments or emergency support.
- Under **Digital Risks**, participants may mention scams, fake job offers, false information, online hate, fear of surveillance, expensive data, broken phones, lack of privacy or not knowing which websites are official.

The conclusion we want to arrive together with the group, is that **although most of us see a phone as a luxury (thinking of the latest iPhone), for the lives of migrants, a lot of times one device is an essential tool** for: understanding their surroundings, communicating with loved ones, taking care of legal issues, applying for jobs, school work, translation and local communication and much more. A central tool for adaptation and subsistence in a hosting community, a lifeline.

Closes this short introduction by explaining that digital inclusion is not only about having a phone. It is also about having access, skills, confidence, language, trust and knowledge of how local digital systems work.

Digital Privilege Walk

After analyzing lifelines and risks, **explain that the next activity will help the group understand how different people experience the digital world in very different ways.** Each participant, pair or small group should receive one persona card. Participants should read the card silently and imagine the digital life of that person.

Make sure to remind the group:

"You are not answering as yourself. You are answering as your persona."

Ask participants to stand on the starting line and explain the movement rules, every round you will shout out a prompt and participants must:

- **Walk one step forward** if the statement is easy, true or accessible for your persona.
- **Stay still** if the statement is partly true, uncertain or depends on the situation.
- **Take one step back** if the statement is difficult, risky or not accessible for your persona.

The facilitator should give participants a few seconds after each prompt to decide and move. If participants are unsure, they can stay still. The aim is not to find the "perfect" answer, but to reflect from the perspective of the persona.

The statements are categorized to reveal different layers of the digital divide.

<p>"The Young Parent" 30-year-old mother from Ukraine, refugee in Latvia.</p> <p><u>Key Vulnerabilities/Privileges</u> High motivation, low previous digital exposure. Focus on family support.</p> <p><u>Digital Context</u> Relies on spouse/community for navigation. Struggling to learn language/gov apps.</p>	<p>"The Institutionally-Dependent Youth" 18-year-old male from Morocco, recently exited the protection system in Spain.</p> <p><u>Key Vulnerabilities/Privileges</u> High vulnerability. Post-minority legal limbo. Institutional dependency/precarious independence.</p> <p><u>Digital Context</u> Access restricted by shelter rules. No bank account for online payments.</p>	<p>"The Rural Youth" 18-year-old female from a village near Riga (LV). Unemployed.</p> <p><u>Key Vulnerabilities/Privileges</u> Citizen, but geographic isolation. Lower economic status.</p> <p><u>Digital Context</u> Shared family PC (old). Slow/unstable internet. Basic skills only.</p>	<p>"The Local Digital Native" 22-year-old male from Lisbon (PT). Finished university. Parents act as financial safety net.</p> <p><u>Key Vulnerabilities/Privileges</u> High economic & social capital. Dominant language.</p> <p><u>Digital Context</u> Owns MacBook & iPhone. High-speed fiber. Creating a startup.</p>	<p>"The Digital Refugee" 24-year-old male from Venezuela, living in Madrid (ES). Asylum seeker. University studies interrupted by the country's economic and political crisis.</p> <p><u>Key Vulnerabilities/Privileges</u> High cultural capital (interrupted education), low legal status. Native Spanish Speaker.</p> <p><u>Digital Context</u> Phone screen cracked. Fear of surveillance. Credentials not recognized.</p>	<p>"The Intersectionality Case" 21-year-old non-binary person from Brazil living in Portugal.</p> <p><u>Key Vulnerabilities/Privileges</u> Native language, but faces discrimination.</p> <p><u>Digital Context</u> Active on social media but faces harassment. Good skills, mental health strain.</p>
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Foundations (Economic & Social Capital) These statements establish the baseline inequalities that prefigure digital access.

1. "If you have citizenship in the country where you currently live, take one step forward."
2. "If English is your first language or you speak the local language fluently, take one step forward."
3. "If you have ever gone to sleep hungry because you didn't have money for food, take one step backward."
4. "If you can open a bank account without difficulty, take one step forward."
5. "If you are not afraid of the police or immigration authorities stopping you, take one step forward."

The First Digital Divide (Hardware & Connectivity) These statements address the physical access to technology.

- "If you own a personal laptop or computer that is less than 5 years old, take one step forward."
- "If your primary access to the internet is through a mobile data plan that you have to ration or limit, take one step backward."
- "If you have unlimited, high-speed Wi-Fi in your private home, take one step forward."
- "If you rely on public Wi-Fi (libraries, cafes) to do your homework or job applications, take one step backward."
- "If you have a quiet, private space where you can make a video call without interruption, take one step forward."

The Second Digital Divide (Skills & Literacy) These statements address the capability to use tools effectively.

- "If you know how to create and format a CV (Europass) and convert it to PDF without help, take one step forward."
- "If you can easily identify a 'phishing' scam or fake news article, take one step forward."
- "If you rely on your children or younger friends to translate emails or government websites for you, take one step backward."
- "If you know how to use collaborative tools like Google Drive, Zoom, or Trello, take one step forward."
- "If you have ever felt 'stupid' or embarrassed because you couldn't figure out how to use a new app or device, take one step backward."

The Third Digital Divide (Outcomes & Rights) These statements address the ability to translate digital usage into life chances.

- "If you can use the internet to find a job that matches your qualifications, take one step forward."
- "If you have ever avoided posting on social media because you feared harassment regarding your race, gender, or religion, take one step backward."
- "If you worry that your digital communications are being monitored by a government (here or back home), take one step backward."
- "If you see people who look like you represented positively in the tech world or online media, take one step forward."
- "If you can access your medical records or legal documents digitally at any time, take one step forward."

After the final statement, ask everyone to stay where they are and look around silently and allow a short pause before speaking. This helps participants visually notice the distance created between personas.

Then start picking their brains:

- **What do you notice?**
- **Which personas moved forward most often?**
- **Which personas stayed behind or moved backwards?**
- **Was the difference mainly about money, language, legal status, devices, confidence, safety or social support?**
- **What does this activity show us about the idea that "everyone has a phone, so everyone is digitally included"?**

Bring everyone back to the circle and explain that the digital divide has three important dimensions: **Access, Skills and Culture**.

Access means having internet, devices, data, electricity and safe spaces.

Skills means knowing how to use tools, forms, passwords, email, AI, translation and digital services.

Culture means understanding how digital systems work in the host country: which websites are official, how to write formal messages, what is normal to pay for, and how to recognise scams.

You can highlight that some personas had strong digital skills but still faced discrimination, legal insecurity, fear of surveillance or lack of recognition. Which shows that digital inclusion is not only technical; it is also social, economic and political.

Digital safety and the 3-Click Rule

Connect the previous Digital Privilege Walk with online risks and conclude with the group that when people have urgent needs: housing, documents, work, transport, family support – they may be highly exposed to manipulation online.

Here are the three main digital threat areas that can affect young migrants:

- misinformation;
- surveillance and privacy risks;
- trafficking, smuggling, exploitation or scam offers.

Keep moving through the slides until you reach John's offer with following example message:
"Hey, I am John. I can provide a work permit for only 500€. The process takes only two weeks. If you are interested, click the link."

www.scammingpeople0909.xom/givemeyour500eurosfornothing

Discuss with the group:

- What makes this message suspicious?
- What pressure is the message creating?
- What could happen if someone clicks, pays or sends documents?
- What should the person check before answering?

After collecting answers and engaging in discussion with the group start introducing the **3-Click Rule** as a simple digital harm-reduction method.

- First, participants should **check the profile or source**. They should ask: Who is behind the message? Is this an official organisation, a known service, or an unknown person?
- Second, they should **reverse search or verify the content**. They can search the text, image, phone number, organisation name or link. If there is a photo, they can use Google Lens or another reverse image search tool.
- Third, they should **review the results before acting**. They should compare information with official websites, trusted organisations or youth workers before paying money, clicking links or sending documents.

Make sure to highlight how **google lens and checking social media accounts activity** can support this process!

You can close this part of the activity with the message:

"The goal is not to tell you guys: 'Do not use the internet. The goal is: Do not navigate alone, under pressure, and without checking.'"

After, stop in the image of the messenger who offered the work permit for 500€ and ask participants if anyone knows who John is. After hearing some guesses, showcase that this is actually the picture of a real scammer who scammed thousands of people of millions of euros/liras through a ponzi scheme, here's some context:

Mehmet Aydın, known in Turkey as "Tosuncuk", created **Çiftlik Bank / Farm Bank**, an online game that looked like a digital farm. Users bought virtual animals and products, believing their money was also being invested in real farms and would generate profit. In reality, the system was reported as a Ponzi-style scam: early users were paid with money from new users, which created trust and attracted more people. The scheme collected money from thousands of people before collapsing in 2018. Mehmet is now in prison.

Finish by **building a Digital First Aid Kit together with participants on a flipchart**. Ask the group: "If we had to create a kit with the most important habits, practices and knowledge to stay safe online, what would we include?" Collect answers and write them on the flipchart. Guide participants to cover areas such as:

- Using strong, unique passwords and a password manager
- Enabling two-factor authentication
- Recognising phishing messages and suspicious links
- Applying the 3-Click Rule before trusting any offer
- Keeping software and apps updated
- Using official websites and verified sources only
- Not sharing personal documents or money under pressure
- Knowing who to contact if something feels wrong (trusted adult, organisation, hotline)
- Using secure Wi-Fi and avoiding public networks for sensitive tasks
- Checking privacy settings on social media

Debriefing

At the end of the activity, bring participants back into a circle and help them connect the experience of the Digital Privilege Walk and info-session, with real-life digital safety. The debriefing should move from what they observed, to what they understood about digital inequality, and finally to how they can protect themselves and others online.

Keep the tone supportive and practical: the goal is not to create fear around digital tools, but to help participants recognise that digital inclusion depends on access, skills, language, confidence, safety and trusted support.

Close by reinforcing the 3-Click Rule as a simple habit they can use before trusting online offers, messages, links or requests for money/documents.

Some questions to support reflection and debriefing process

What did you notice during the activity?

Who moved forward? Who stayed behind?

What made some personas face more difficulties?

What digital risks appeared in the suspicious message?

What are the 3 steps of the 3-Click Rule?

Why is it important to check the source before trusting a message?

Why should we be careful before sending documents, money or personal information online?

RESOURCES

- Presentation deck: The Connected Migrant: <https://canva.link/womstiyics7ra8v3>
- Projector and speakers
- Laptop for the facilitator
- Persona cards for the Digital Privilege Walk: <https://canva.link/ng6c8rxzklmzmre>
- Tape, string or chairs to mark the starting line
- Open space for movement
- Flipchart or whiteboard
- Markers
- Prepared flipchart with two columns: Digital Lifeline and Digital Risk
- Example suspicious message / scam message
- Optional: smartphone, tablet or laptop for checking links, profiles or images
- Optional: Google Lens or reverse image search tool
- Optional bilingual glossary
- Printed or digital reflection questions

Inclusion and Accessibility Notes:

- Use simple, realistic examples and avoid overly technical language, especially for participants with lower digital confidence.
- Avoid asking participants to share personal experiences of scams, harassment, migration-related risks or other sensitive online situations unless they choose to do so.
- Offer pair or small-group discussion before plenary sharing, so participants can reflect in a safer and less exposed way.
- If the activity includes checking websites, messages or posts, use fictional or sample materials rather than participants' real accounts or private content.
- Keep the tone practical and reassuring, so participants leave feeling more capable and not more afraid of using digital tools.

Duration

90 - 120 minutes

AI TOOLS AND ETHICAL PROMPTING FOR EVERYDAY LIFE

This activity introduces young migrants to the practical uses of AI tools in everyday life to organise ideas, support writing, translation and problem-solving. The info-session also helps them reflect on how to use AI critically, safely and responsibly whilst focusing on useful practice, basics of prompting and ethical awareness of Artificial Intelligence.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

By the end of the activity, participants will be able to:

- **Recognise how AI tools can support everyday integration tasks**, such as translation, writing, studying, job applications, interview preparation and simplifying difficult information.
- **Explain the basic structure of an effective AI prompt using the PCTF formula:** Persona, Context, Task and Format.
- **Improve weak prompts** by adding clear context, a specific task, a useful format and basic safety instructions.
- **Use AI critically to support a simple employment-related tasks**, such as improving a short cover letter without inventing false experience or personal information.
- **Identify key ethical and safety risks of AI use**, including privacy, hallucinations, bias, overdependence and the need to fact-check important information.
- **Create practical digital safety rules for a shared Digital First Aid Kit**, connected to responsible AI use, privacy or online decision-making.

METHODOLOGIES

Guided digital demonstration

Prompt-writing practice

PCTF method

Pair work/Small-group problem-solving

Scenario-based learning

AI-supported writing practice

Critical digital literacy

Ethical reflection

Digital First Aid Kit creation

ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION

Energizer

Participants stand in small groups. Each group receives a very vague instruction, such as “draw something useful”, “organise the room”, or “prepare a message”. They try to complete the task quickly, but the instruction is intentionally unclear. After one minute, the facilitator gives a more specific version, for example: “draw a simple poster inviting young people to a football activity, using three colours and one clear title.”

After the second attempt, ask participants what changed. This short energizer introduces the main idea of the session: the quality of the instruction changes the quality of the result. It creates a natural bridge to AI prompting and the PCTF formula.

Introduction to AI tools

After the energizer, use the discussion to connect the activity with the main topic of the session: how to communicate better with AI tools. Explain that AI can be useful in everyday life, especially for tasks such as translation, writing messages, studying, preparing for job interviews, simplifying difficult texts or organising information. At the same time, make clear that AI is supposed to be a support tool that allows humans to focus on creative tasks, decision making and offload tedious repetitive tasks for example. It is not a magic solution, and it can make mistakes, invent information, reproduce bias or create privacy risks.

Make sure to ask the group:

- Who has already used AI?
- What have you used it for?
- What could AI help a migrant or newcomer with?
- What could be risky?

Collect a few quick answers and then introduce the idea that the quality of what we get from AI depends strongly on the quality of the prompt and the information (docs, images, excel, etc.) we give to it. You can also ask your participants what they know about AI, prompting, and how they currently use AI (for what purposes and how they go about prompting, for example).

The Art of Prompting: PCTF

Using the projector, start introducing the PCTF formula:

- **P - Persona**
- **C - Context**
- **T - Task**
- **F - Format**

Explains each part with simple examples of how participants can go about designing prompts with this framework.

Persona means telling AI who it should act as.

For example: act as a job coach, language tutor, digital safety mentor, bureaucracy decoder or cultural guide.

Context means explaining the situation.

For example: I am a young migrant, I have B1 Portuguese, I only have a smartphone, I am looking for my first job, I do not understand official language very well.

Task means saying exactly what AI should do.

For example: write a cover letter, simplify a text, make a checklist, prepare interview questions, explain warning signs of a scam.

Format means saying how the answer should look.

For example: bullet points, table, short WhatsApp message, checklist, simple language, role-play dialogue or step-by-step plan.

When everyone is on the same page about PCTF, showcase the difference in performance between a weak prompt and PCTF prompt, **starting with a weak prompt like:**

"Help me find a job."

Then, improve it live:

"Act as a job coach. I am a young migrant with B1 Portuguese and experience in hotel cleaning, but I only have a smartphone and limited mobile data. Give me five realistic job-search steps in simple bullet points. Do not ask for personal data."

Discuss and ask participants what changed between the first and second prompt. The goal should be to arrive at the conclusion that the **second prompt gives the AI: a specific role, a situation or specific context where it's working, a clear task the AI needs to work on, a specific format to deliver the task.** When we understand this, we can start using AI ethically and making the most of its potential. You can also emphasize that is also very powerful to help you think things through, access information fast. People start using it wrong the second they are lazy and start telling AI to think for them or replace work that THEY should have done!

Fix the Prompt

In the next section of the activity it's time to get right into practice! Divide your youngsters into small groups. Each group will receive one weak prompt (written in paper, chosen from a flipchart or sent as a text message). Their task is to improve it using the PCTF formula.

Here's some example weak prompts you can use:

- "Write a CV for a cleaner."
- "Make a lesson plan for learning Portuguese."
- "Explain how to get a health card."
- "Help me find a house."
- "Write a message to my boss."
- "Tell me what this contract means."

Each group rewrites the prompt by adding a persona, context, task, and format. Pro tip: Remind them that the prompt should not ask participants to share real personal information. And that it's useful to include reminders such as "do not invent information", "use simple language", "give general guidance only", or "remind me to check official sources".

After around 15/20 minutes, **groups should present their improved prompts.** After each presentation, ask the rest of the group:

- Is the persona clear?
- Is the context realistic?
- Is the task specific?
- Is the format useful?
- Is the prompt safe?
- Does it avoid sharing personal data?

While checking everyone's work, mediate the room, provide short feedback on the prompts and reinforce that a good prompt is not only more efficient, but also safer and more inclusive.

AI cover letter practice

After the prompting exercise, keep the group moving into the AI rabbit hole: explain that next participants will practise using AI for a realistic integration task: preparing a short cover letter for a job.

Begin by typing this raw text onto ChatGPT or the AI of your choice:

"I want job cleaning. I clean hotel in home country 2 years. I fast. I clean good. I want work night shift."

Before running any prompt, **task participants with working in pairs and try to improve the text manually and turn it into a cover letter**, without AI in 5/10 minutes. They should make it clearer and more polite, but they should not invent experience or qualifications.

After a few minutes, **add the AI prompt below to the text you typed in the AI** and run the prompt:

"Rewrite this as a polite cover letter for a housekeeping position. Emphasise reliability. Use simple language and do not invent experience."

Give a few minutes for participants to test the prompt on an AI tool if devices and internet are available. If not, you can test it live on the projector.

Then, **run the same prompt again on a different chat and ask participants to suggest a few additional instructions to tailor the result to our needs:**

- "Make it more formal."
- "Shorten it."
- "Make it sound more authentic and less artificial."

When you reach a good enough result **compare the different results between the first prompt and the tailored version** and ask:

- Which version sounds most authentic?
- Which version sounds too artificial?
- What should never be invented in a CV or cover letter?
- What personal information should not be uploaded into AI?
- How can AI support someone's voice without replacing it?

Highlight that AI can help someone express themselves more clearly, especially in a second language, but it should not create a fake identity, fake qualifications or unrealistic promises

Ethical AI and the Golden Rules

Time to move on from prompting. Explain that AI has three important risks that young people should always remember.

The first risk is privacy and surveillance. AI tools may process or store information in ways users do not fully control. This is especially sensitive for migrants, refugees, asylum seekers, undocumented people or people with vulnerable legal status.

The second risk is hallucination. AI can give false information with confidence. This is dangerous when people ask about law, migration, health, social benefits or official procedures.

The third risk is bias. AI can reproduce stereotypes or unfair assumptions about nationality, gender, religion, language, migration status or social background.

So what are the golden rules? Start with the one below:

Never upload personally identifiable information into AI tools.

Give some examples:

- full names;
- addresses;
- phone numbers;
- case numbers;
- ID or passport numbers;
- medical information;
- legal documents;
- photos of faces;
- asylum or migration documents.

The second golden rule is:

Fact-check. Always.

Explain that AI can be used to simplify language, prepare questions, organise ideas or draft texts. However, it should not be treated as an official legal, medical, migration or social-service authority.

Then as we're getting closer to debriefing ask participants to complete the sentence below with what they learned from today in a word or two:

"Before I use AI for something important, I should..."

Participants may answer: remove personal data, check official websites, ask a youth worker, ask a lawyer, ask a public service, compare different sources or not act immediately.

Debriefing: AI Practical Rules for Youth and closing

To close the activity, invite participants to stop using devices and return their attention to the group. Do a little bit of the 3W's reflection process (What? So What? Now What?), then give a post-it to each participant, have them write one practical rule they want to remember when using AI tools. The rule should be simple, concrete and connected to safe, critical or useful AI use.

Examples can include:

- "I will not upload personal documents to AI."
- "I will remove names, addresses and case numbers before using AI."
- "I will use PCTF to make my prompts clearer."
- "I will not believe an AI answer without checking it."
- "I will not let AI invent experience for my CV or cover letter."
- "I will ask a trusted person or official service before making important decisions."

Participants place their post-its on a flipchart titled **What we learned about AI today**. Read some of the rules aloud and connect them back to the main learning points of the session: AI can support writing, learning, translation, job preparation and organisation, but it must be used with clear instructions, privacy protection and critical thinking.

RESOURCES

- Computer, tablet or mobile phone for each participant or pair
- Facilitator laptop
- Internet connection
- Access to ChatGPT or another AI tool
- Presentation deck: AI Tools and Ethical Use of AI: <https://canva.link/cxeykyymb42s6il>
- Projector and speakers
- Weak prompt cards
- AI safety rules slide or handout
- Flipchart or whiteboard
- Post-its
- Pens or markers
- Paper Digital First Aid Kit Flipchart
- Optional bilingual glossary
- Optional printed version of prompts and examples for participants without devices

Duration

75 minutes

DIGITAL ESCAPE ROOM: MIGRANT PATHWAY

This activity uses a digital escape room format to help participants explore common situations related to integration, services and everyday decision-making. Through clues, teamwork and problem-solving, they practise digital navigation and critical thinking in an interactive way. The focus is on collaboration, orientation and learning through challenge.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

By the end of the activity, participants will be able to:

- **Explore key integration pathways by solving digital challenges** connected to rights, support services, education, training, daily-life situations and local opportunities.
- **Identify where young migrants can look for help or information in a new community**, including public services, youth organisations, education/training providers and local support structures.
- **Apply teamwork, communication and problem-solving skills** by discussing clues, making decisions together and completing the escape room challenges as a group.
- **Practise digital navigation skills by using the Genially platform**, following instructions, interacting with digital clues and moving through an online learning environment.
- **Reflect on how the knowledge gained during the escape room can be useful in real-life** integration situations, such as finding support, understanding options or making safer decisions.

METHODOLOGIES

Gamification
(Escape Room)

Experimental learning

Collaborative
problem-solving

Guided reflection and
group debriefing

ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION

Preparation before the activity

Before the activity, organise the room for small-group work, with each group having access to one device and a stable internet connection. The Genially escape room link should be tested in advance to make sure all clues, buttons, letters and final answers work correctly. Prepare the projector, speaker, visible timer, rules slide, and a simple answer key with possible hints for each challenge. If possible, the link should be available as a QR code or short link to make access easier. As a backup, the facilitator may prepare printed screenshots or a simplified paper version of the main challenges in case of technical problems.

Energizer

Start with a 5-minute energizer to create a positive atmosphere and encourage teamwork. The energizer should be short and interactive, helping participants feel comfortable working with others before the main activity begins.

Introduction to the Escape Room

After this first moment, follows a 15-minute briefing. In this moment, introduce the title and purpose of the activity, explaining that participants will go through a digital escape room called “Migrant Pathways”, where they will solve challenges connected to real-life integration situations. Explain the rules, the timing (30 minutes), and the expected group dynamic: all team members should participate, discuss options together, and support one another during the activity.

Finishing this introduction, explain how to use the Genially platform, the mechanics, how to move through the tasks, and what to do if the group gets stuck.

Rules:

- Work as a team and make sure everyone participates.
- Read each challenge carefully and discuss before choosing an answer.
- You have 30 minutes to complete the escape room and collect all the letters.
- Use only your team device and the Genially activity to solve the tasks.
- If you get stuck, try together first, then ask the facilitator for a hint if needed.
- Be respectful, supportive, and focused, because the goal is to learn together.

After the briefing, divide participants into small groups and share the link to the escape room. The 30-minute gameplay phase then begins. During this phase, each group works through digital clues, mini-scenarios and problem-solving tasks connected to integration pathways. The challenges include identifying where to find support services, understanding basic rights, recognising education or training opportunities, making decisions in practical daily-life situations, and solving tasks that require communication and cooperation. During the gameplay, monitor the groups, keep track of time, and only intervene when technical support or a small hint is needed.

Once the escape room ends, bring the group together for a 30-minute debriefing.

Together with the participants you will recall the journey and the challenges.

- What happened during the activity?
- What was easy for your team?
- What was difficult?
- How did you feel during the activity?
- How it was working in teams to solve the tasks?

The goal is to connect the experience to the learning objectives helping participants move from “what happened” to “what we learned.”

What did we learn today?

To close the debriefing, ask participants

- “One thing I will remember from this activity is...”
- How could you use what you learned today in everyday life?

If the activity is implemented with youth workers, you can also ask how this tool could be adapted to their local context and to the real needs of young migrants they work with.

This activity should be implemented as a practical, safe, and engaging learning experience in which participants build knowledge through action, teamwork, and reflection rather than through formal instruction.

RESOURCES

- 1 Laptop per group + 1 for the facilitator
- Genially link
- Projector
- Speaker
- Flipchart or Whiteboard

Duration

90 minutes

OPPORTUNITY NAVIGATOR

FINDING COURSES, JOBS AND LOCAL SUPPORT ONLINE

This activity helps participants search for useful opportunities online in a more focused and practical way. They explore how to find courses, job offers and local support services, compare options, and identify which sources are relevant and trustworthy. The focus is on digital navigation, informed choice and connecting online information to real-life next steps.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

By the end of the activity, participants will be able to:

- **Search for relevant opportunities** online by each team finding at least one validated opportunity in each of the seven categories and recording the evidence (link + screenshot).
- **Improve their digital judgement and safety** by each participant applying a **simple Trust Check** to at least two sources and identifying two “red flags” of unsafe or unreliable information.
- **Completing a Personal Opportunity Map** with at least 5 saved opportunities and one concrete next step they will take within 7 days.

METHODOLOGIES

Gamification

Peer learning

Guided discovery

Guided reflection and group debriefing

Action planning

Facilitator coaching

ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION

Enter the room and welcome the group in a calm and encouraging way, creating a safe atmosphere for participation. Introduce briefly the purpose of the activity, explaining that the session is about learning how to find real opportunities and useful support online, while also learning how to recognise whether a website or source can be trusted. From the beginning make clear that the goal is not to search as fast as possible, but to help participants find options that are truly relevant to their own lives. A simple online safety reminder is also given, especially around avoiding suspicious websites and not sharing personal information on unknown platforms.

Introduce the activity by showing participants how to search in a practical and realistic way.

- Open a search engine and type a real search such as “IEFP emprego Fundão” or “iefponline ofertas de emprego” to look for official employment and training opportunities.
- Check the results before clicking and choose an official source, such as the IEFP website or iefponline, instead of an unknown page.
- Open the result and verify the key information: whether the page is really from IEFP, whether it offers employment or training services, and whether it includes clear contact or service information.
- If participants need local support, search “CLAIM Fundão II” and open the Municipality of Fundão page to show how to confirm that it is an official local service supporting migrants in areas such as work, education and training, health, housing, and regularisation.
- Point out the safety check: prefer pages that clearly show the institution name, explain their service, and provide contact information; avoid pages with suspicious links, unclear ownership, or pressure to pay quickly. IEFP and the Municipality of Fundão both provide identifiable official service pages.
- Save the useful result by copying the link or taking a screenshot, so participants keep a real contact point such as iefponline for jobs/training or CLAIM Fundão II for local support

(This part should be adapted to specific websites and services in each country)

PERSONAL OPPORTUNITY

Name:
Category:
Why it helps me:
Trust note:
Next step:

Name:
Category:
Why it helps me:
Trust note:
Next step:

MY GOAL
RIGHT NOW

Once participants understand the aim of the activity, invite them to work in pairs or small groups to begin exploring opportunities and support services online. Explain that they should focus on finding options that are relevant, realistic, and useful, rather than collecting as many links as possible. Throughout the activity, move around the room, supporting participants with search terms, translation needs, navigation difficulties, and basic digital tasks such as opening websites, finding contact details, identifying deadlines, or saving screenshots. You should pay particular attention to participants who seem hesitant, overwhelmed, or less experienced, offering light support without taking over the process.

As participants search, introduce the Trust Check as a simple habit for judging whether an online source seems reliable. Encourage participants to look at who created the website, why it exists, whether the information is recent, and whether there are clear contact details or signs of legitimacy. At the same time, invite them to notice warning signs such as suspicious links, unrealistic promises, poor transparency, pressure to act quickly, or requests for money.

After the searching phase, support participants in moving from exploration to personal choice. Each participant is invited to select the opportunities or services that are most relevant to their own situation and organise them into a Personal Opportunity Map.

Explain that this map is not simply a collection of links, but a practical tool to help participants reflect on what is useful for them, why it matters, whether it seems trustworthy, and what they could do next.

At the end of the activity, participants are invited into a short and structured sharing moment to help them reflect on what they found and learn from each other. Instead of an open discussion where only a few people speak, each participant or pair is asked to share their results using a simple structure.

First, they present one opportunity or service they found, saying what it is and why it could be useful.

Debriefing

After the sharing round, lead a short debriefing to help participants reflect on what they found, how they searched, and what they want to do next. The aim is to help them recognise that finding opportunities online is not only about getting results, but also about choosing sources that are relevant, trustworthy, and useful for their own situation. Keep the reflection simple and practical, encouraging participants to think about what helped them during the search, what made a source seem safe or unsafe, and what action they feel ready to take after the activity.

- What happened during your search?
- What did you notice while looking for opportunities or services?
- What did you discover about finding information online?
- What will you remember from this activity for next time?

RESOURCES

- Laptops
- Internet connection / Wi-Fi / mobile data
- Projector
- Personal Opportunity Map template(to be printed): <https://canva.link/h5mqg1bkc6yywg6>
- Trust Check Card + Presentation: <https://canva.link/du0u64prq4ofr0>
- Printed list of local opportunities and support services
- Pens
- Paper
- Markers
- Optional folder / shared drive to save participants' outputs

Inclusion and Accessibility Notes

- For participants with lower digital confidence, prepare a short list of pre-selected websites or QR codes first, so they start from trusted options instead of having to search from zero.
- For participants with language barriers, allow them to search in their preferred language first and then compare results with the local-language version of the same platform or service.
- For young people who may feel overwhelmed by too many options, reduce the task to one category only at first, such as "one course" or "one support service," before asking them to compare several opportunities.
- If some participants have limited device access, organise the task in pairs with clear roles, for example one person searches and the other notes useful links, deadlines or contact points.
- For participants who may feel anxious around employment or bureaucracy, include examples of local youth support, language courses, mentoring, volunteering or community services, not only jobs, so the activity feels reachable and relevant.
- If reading long webpages becomes a barrier, use a simple comparison grid with headings such as what it is, who it is for, deadline, location, and how to apply, so participants can organise information more easily.

Duration
90 min

DIGITAL PEDDYPAPER

This activity uses gamified city-based learning, teamwork, digital missions, intercultural interaction, and reflective debriefing to develop participants' cooperation, local orientation, digital creativity, communication skills, and sense of belonging in the community.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

By the end of the activity, participants will be able to:

- Enable participants to develop teamwork and intercultural communication skills in a real-life context, by collaborating in mixed groups of local and migrant young people to complete challenges, navigate the city and support each other.
- Support participants in exploring and engaging with the local environment through interactive digital tools, using the city as a learning space rather than only as a physical location.
- Encourage participants to interact safely and respectfully with local people, local services and public spaces, helping young migrants understand everyday customs, useful places and informal rules of the city.
- Guide participants in using creative and digital expression to document their experience through photos, videos, short texts and group missions.
- Strengthen participants' sense of belonging by helping them identify places, people and services.
- Support participants in reflecting on intercultural learning, local discovery and cooperation, by sharing at least one meaningful moment from the activity during the final reflection.

METHODOLOGIES

Group Formation

Cooperative learning

City Exploration Activity

Guided reflection and group debriefing

Intercultural peer learning

Community interaction

ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION

Preparation before the activity

Before implementing the activity, prepare the Bound on the ActionBound platform. This should be done using a computer, because it is easier to build the route, insert the stages, write the missions, add coordinates and test the full game.

You should first choose the city area where the activity will happen. The route should not be too long and should include places that help participants understand the city in different ways: a public square, a cultural space, a place connected to innovation or employment, a library or service, a market area, a park or another public meeting point.

The activity should not become only a historical tour. The purpose is not that participants memorise facts about the city. The purpose is that they use the city to meet each other, interact with local people, discover useful places, solve small problems together and reflect on what makes a place welcoming for newcomers.

For this reason, each stage should include a balance between information and action. A good stage can include a short explanation of the place, one creative mission, one interaction task and one reflection question. Try to avoid making all the stages only quizzes, because this can make the activity feel like a school test. The strongest missions are usually the ones where participants have to talk, observe, create, decide or collaborate.

When creating the Bound, select multiplayer mode, because participants will work in teams. If possible, the Bound should also be set so that stages are selectable, especially if there are many teams. This allows groups to start in different places and avoids having everyone arriving at the same spot at the same time.

The most useful ActionBound elements for this activity are:

Stage: used to divide the route into different parts. Each stage can correspond to one place in the city.

Find spot: used when participants must physically go to a specific location. Add the GPS coordinates, and participants follow the map, arrow and distance indication.

Mission: used for creative or practical tasks, such as taking a photo, recording a video, writing an answer, asking someone a question, or solving a challenge.

Upload photo/video/audio: used to document the experience and create material for the final reflection.

Quiz: used for short questions about the city, the place or the topic. This can add points and motivation, but it should not dominate the activity.

After building the Bound, we advise your team to test it physically. This means walking the route with the app, checking if the coordinates work, if the instructions are clear, if the stages are safe and if the timing is realistic. You should also check if participants will have mobile data or Wi-Fi, and if the activity can still work if one group has technical problems.

When the Bound is ready, publish it online, download and print the QR code. This QR code will be scanned by participants at the start of the activity.

Example: How we used ActionBound in Fundão

In our Fundão version, the Bound was designed with five stages, each connected to a different dimension of integration.

The first stage was **Praça do Município**, used as a civic and symbolic starting point. Participants were invited to see the square not only as a historical place, but as a meeting point where locals pass by and newcomers may feel curious, lost, welcomed or invisible. The missions asked teams to record a short introduction video, choose a symbol that represented Fundão, and share interesting facts about the places each group member came from. This helped participants start the activity by getting to know each other.

The second stage was **A Moagem - Cidade do Engenho e das Artes**, used to explore culture and creative expression. Participants created a human sculpture, recorded a silent video about an emotion a newcomer may feel when arriving in a new city, and answered a quiz about what can happen in a cultural space. This stage showed that culture is not only something people watch, but something they can join, create and share.

The third stage was the **Incubadora/FabLab**, used to connect integration with innovation. Participants learned that small cities can also be places where ideas, businesses and digital solutions grow. They reflected on one problem young people, migrants or newcomers may face in Fundão and imagined a solution that could be created with the support of an incubator or FabLab. This stage helped participants move from “adapting to the city” to “helping shape the city”.

The fourth stage was the **Biblioteca Municipal and Praça Municipal**, used to connect formal and informal learning. Participants discovered the library as a place for books, study, information, digital tools and community activities, and the market area as a place for everyday encounters. They searched for a famous Portuguese author, researched three facts about him, and spoke with someone working at the library to learn how the library can be used and what activities were happening there.

The fifth stage was **Parque Verde**, used as the final public space for belonging, leisure and connection. Participants explored how parks and open spaces can support inclusion because people do not need money or perfect language skills to sit, walk, play, talk or spend time together. They asked a local person to teach them three expressions used in Fundão, recorded a group dance from a country other than their own, and completed a final hidden facilitator challenge.

This example can be adapted to any city. The important point is not to copy Fundão exactly, but to understand the logic: each location should help participants discover one part of local life and complete one meaningful integration challenge.

Introduction and icebreaker

At the beginning of the session, welcome participants and explain the activity. You should make it clear that this is not only a competition. The goal is to discover the city, work as a team, interact with people respectfully and create new connections between local and migrant participants.

Because the activity involves young locals and young migrants, it is important to begin with a light icebreaker. One possible energiser is the **ball counting game**.

Participants stand in a circle. The group passes a ball from person to person while counting the passes: one, two, three, four and so on. When the group reaches ten, the person holding the ball creates a new rule. For example: "Every time we say three, the person with the ball must clap twice." The group starts again and continues counting. Every time they reach ten, a new rule is added. The game becomes more difficult because participants need to remember all the rules while still cooperating.

Keep the energiser fun and not too competitive. Instead of eliminating participants for mistakes, it is better to restart or laugh together. The aim is to create energy, attention and group connection before going into the city.

Group formation

After the icebreaker, the facilitator creates the teams. Ideally, each team should include both local and migrant participants. You should also consider language, gender balance, age, confidence and digital skills.

Depending on the size of the group, you can create between two and ten teams. A good team size is four to six participants. If the team is too small, it may lack diversity. If it is too large, some participants may become passive.

Each team should have at least one mobile phone with internet connection and enough battery. If possible, encourage teams to share roles so that the same person is not always controlling the phone.

If you want you can suggest and address some roles:

Navigator: follows the map and helps the team move safely.

Reader: reads the instructions aloud.

Reporter: writes the answers and uploads photos or videos.

Connector: makes sure everyone is included in the discussion.

Local guide: if there is a local participant in the team, they can help with orientation, but should not do everything alone.

Language helper: supports translation or explanation when needed.

To keep it interesting, you may suggest teams to rotate roles after each stage, so that participants practise different skills.

Instructions and app setup

Ask participants to download the ActionBound app. To save time, this can be done before the session by sending participants a message asking them to install the app in advance. When the app is installed, show the QR code of the Bound. Each team scans the QR code and enters the game. Check that all groups are inside the correct Bound before they leave. Before starting, give the safety and inclusion rules. These rules should also be included inside the Bound.

-
- Participants should stay with their team at all times.
 - Nobody should walk alone.
 - They should cross roads carefully, respect traffic rules and avoid running.
 - They should not enter private spaces unless the mission clearly says they can and the place is public or previously agreed.
 - They should ask permission before taking photos or videos of people.
 - They should not film children.
 - If a local person does not want to answer, they should thank them politely and move on.
 - If the group gets lost or feels uncomfortable, they should call the facilitator.

Remind participants that the activity is about respectful interaction, not forcing people to participate. A successful team is not only the team with the most points, but the team that communicates well, includes everyone and respects the city.

When all teams are ready, you may start the activity.

City exploration activity

During the activity, teams move through the city following the instructions in the app. They complete missions, answer questions, take photos, record videos and interact with selected spaces or local people.

Stay near the route, move between key points or position themselves in one of the stages. If there are two facilitators, they can divide the route and monitor different areas.

The Bound should include missions that make participants:

- introduce themselves and build team identity;
- observe symbols, signs and public spaces;
- speak with local people in a respectful way;
- discover useful services or cultural places;
- compare customs between different countries or cities;
- create photos, videos or audio recordings;
- solve practical problems together;
- reflect on what makes a city welcoming or difficult for newcomers.

In Fundão, for example, participants did not only answer questions about places. They recorded a team introduction, created a silent video about newcomer emotions, took a human sculpture photo, asked locals for expressions used in the city, visited the library, imagined a solution for a problem faced by young people or migrants, and documented what they discovered.

This type of mission helps local participants see their city through new eyes and helps migrant participants learn how the city works in practice.

Undercover facilitator challenges

The activity can include one or two hidden facilitator challenges. These are moments where a facilitator, volunteer or youth worker is secretly waiting at a certain location in disguise. The app tells teams to “find the undercover facilitator and solve the challenge”.

This adds surprise, humour and human interaction to the Bound. The challenge should be short, safe and connected to the learning objectives.

Undercover Challenge 1 - Incubadora / FabLab: “Play the Marshmallow Challenge”

When found the undercover facilitator gives the group 20 spaghetti sticks, 9cm tape, 9cm yarn/string and 1 marshmallow.

The team has 18 minutes to build the tallest free-standing tower possible, with the marshmallow on top.

Rules:

- use only the materials provided;
- the marshmallow must be on top;
- the tower must stand and support its weight;
- all team members should participate.

This challenge connects well with the FabLab because it is about creativity, prototyping, testing ideas and solving problems together.

Short Reflection Tip:

Help participants understand that this is a game about teamwork, group dynamics, as well as the concept of prototyping and trying different solutions until reaching the desired outcome. Ask them how the process was, what leaders emerged, and what key moments happened in the 18 minutes. Finish by going over the importance of awareness when working in a group, noticing who is more extrovert with a tendency to lead, and who is more shy to speak is a powerful skill especially if we can find a way to bring balance and effective cooperation.

Undercover Challenge 2 - Parque Verde: “Turn the Carpet Challenge”

The undercover facilitator places a carpet, blanket or tarp on the ground. All team members stand on it.

The team must turn the carpet completely over while everyone stays on top of it. Nobody can touch the floor.

Rules:

- everyone starts on the carpet;
- the carpet must be fully turned over;
- if someone touches the floor, the team restarts;
- no pushing or unsafe movements.

This challenge connects well with Parque Verde because it uses public space for play, trust and cooperation. It also shows that teams succeed when they communicate and make space for everyone.

Short Reflection Tip:

Help participants understand that this is a game about cooperation, trust, communication and making space for others. Ask them how the group organised itself, who gave ideas, who helped others balance, and what moments made the challenge easier or harder. Finish by connecting the activity to inclusion: in a group, success is not only reaching the goal, but making sure nobody is left behind or pushed out of the process.

Reflection

When all teams finish the Bound, they return to the meeting point. Invite all participants to stop using their phones and come back to the group.

The reflection starts with **Visual Recall**. Each team looks back at the photos and videos they created during the activity and chooses one that best represents their experience. It can be a funny moment, a difficult challenge, an interesting place, an interaction with a local person, or something that helped them understand the city differently.

Each team presents their chosen photo or video and explains:

- where it was taken;
- what was happening;
- why they chose it;
- what they learned from that moment.

After this, guide a group discussion:

- What helped your team cooperate?
- What was difficult during the activity?
- What did you discover about the city?
- What did you discover about the people in your team?
- What was it like to speak with local people?
- Which place felt most welcoming?
- Which place could be confusing for a newcomer?
- What local custom, word or expression did you learn?
- What could make this city easier to understand for young migrants?
- How can local young people support newcomers without speaking for them?

Connect the answers to the main learning points: integration is not only about services or documents. It is also about everyday encounters, public spaces, language, confidence, shared activities and feeling that one has the right to participate in the city.

RESOURCES

- A computer to create the Bound before the activity;
- An ActionBound facilitator account;
- One mobile phone with internet connection per team;
- The ActionBound app installed on each team's phone;
- A QR code giving access to the Bound;
- A projector or printed QR code to launch the activity;
- A ball for the icebreaker;
- 2 undercover facilitators
- Printed emergency contact sheet with the facilitator's phone number - 1 per team;
- Optional: small prizes or symbolic certificates for all teams;
- Optional: reflective posters or flipcharts for the final debriefing.

ActionBound Link: <https://actionbound.com/bound/youthconnect-peddypaper-PT>

Duration
90 min

05. CONCLUSION

CONCLUSION

Digital inclusion is not only about knowing how to use a computer, Canva, or an AI tool. For young migrants **digital competences are closely connected to autonomy, access to rights, employability, and the ability to build an independent life in a new community.** When young people face barriers such as limited access to devices, unstable internet connection, language difficulties and lack of guidance, digital exclusion can become another layer of social exclusion.

This manual does not claim to solve all the structural challenges faced by young migrants and refugees, but it offers one concrete contribution: a set of non-formal education activities that youth workers, educators, facilitators, and organisations can use to support digital inclusion in a more accessible, participatory, and human-centred way. Through these activities, digital learning is connected to real-life needs.

The goal of this manual is therefore not only to develop digital skills, but to strengthen confidence, participation, and belonging. Each activity was designed to help young people learn by doing, reflect on their own experiences, cooperate with others, and apply digital tools to situations that matter in daily life. At the same time, the manual supports youth workers in creating safer, more inclusive, and more flexible learning environments, where different starting points are recognised and where participants are not judged for what they do not yet know.

Education shapes the way young people access society, not only the way they acquire knowledge. It influences who can understand institutions, claim rights, enter the labour market, and imagine realistic futures for themselves. For young migrants and refugees, this role is even more important, because many of the barriers they face are not only individual, but structural: unfamiliar systems, language gaps, unequal access to information, limited networks, and reduced confidence in public or digital spaces. In this context, **non-formal education is particularly relevant** because it does not start from standardised content alone, but from the realities, experiences, needs, and capacities of the learners. Its participatory, practical and adaptable nature makes it well suited to groups with diverse backgrounds and uneven starting points. By combining digital competence with trust, cooperation, creativity, reflection, and real-life problem-solving, non-formal education can turn digital inclusion into a broader process of social participation and empowerment.

In this sense, the YouthConnect manual should be understood as more than a collection of activities. It is a youth work tool for inclusion, helping educators turn digital learning into a pathway for autonomy, safety, employability, participation, and social connection. Its value lies in its practical use: in the workshops delivered, in the confidence built, in the barriers reduced, and in the moments where young migrants and refugees begin to see digital tools not as obstacles, but as **instruments for building their own future.**

06. CONTACTS

CONTACTS

Get in touch with the YouthConnect partnership

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